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Terrorism, Media Attitudes Towards Migration and Votes: Evidence from France*

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Abstract

This paper investigates media attitudes towards migration in the aftermath of terrorist attacks and examines their impact on voting outcomes. Using natural language processing (NLP) methods, we analyze French news articles on immigration before and after three major terrorist events in 2015 and 2016. Our findings show that the salience of immigration in the French media (especially National media) increased for up to eight weeks following the attacks. In particular, in the first three weeks, where immigration was evoked with Muslims or (in)security-related issues, salience increased fivefold. Furthermore, the tone of reporting became significantly more negative, though this effect was shorter in duration, albeit lasting for at least two weeks. Further, we show how this change in media behaviour have participated to the increase in votes in favor of the main anti-migrant party in France, at the Élections Régionales, held 3 weeks after the November 13 attack. We could estimate a contribution of the media's change in behaviour to the total rise in votes for the Far-right of about 2% on average. In some French localities however, we estimated the contribution to reach more than 12%.

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1 Introduction

This paper offers an illustration of how a short-run dramatic shock like an important terror event observed in democracies, might lead to a change in political outcomes, through the media channel, which may eventually translate into longer lasting, or structural, policy change.

In particular, although the economic impact of terrorism has been extensively studied (see the survey of Sandler and Gaibullov, [2022](#)), one question that remains underexplored is how terrorism shocks backlash on migrants via changes in the behaviour of agents, and especially through changes in the discourse of the media. We are primarily concerned here about the identification of the role of the media in provoking changes in preferences and votes for anti-migrant type policies.

It is important to focus specifically on the role of the media and its discourse about migrants, especially those from Muslim-majority countries. Indeed, one of the key objectives of radical terrorist organizations is to create divisions between Muslim and non-Muslim communities, thus encouraging individuals of Muslim origin to align with their cause in developed countries. If media outlets adopt a more negative stance towards Muslim migrants following terrorist events, this could amplify negative attitudes and lead to stricter policies targeting this group, inadvertently supporting the terrorists' broader goals.

Our analysis focuses on three major terrorist attacks that occurred in France between 2015 and 2016: the Charlie Hebdo/Hyper Cacher events on January 7-9, 2015, the Paris terrorist attacks of November 13, 2015 (targeting the Bataclan concert hall and the Stade de France), and the Bastille Day attack in Nice on July 14, 2016. We hypothesize that these dramatic events significantly influenced media reportings on immigration, particularly with regard to Muslims, for three reasons: (1) the perpetrators were either first- or second-generation migrants from Muslim-majority countries; (2) the attacks targeted important symbols of the French culture and its values; and (3) the attackers were linked to or inspired by Islamist groups, potentially causing confusion in media reporting between Islamist ideology and the Muslim religion, to which many immigrants in France belong.

In the first part of the paper, we evaluate how these acts of terrorism have influenced the discourse on migrants in the news. Specifically, we quantify the corresponding changes in the behavior of the media towards migrants in terms of duration, salience, and tone. We

analyze news articles on immigration published in most French *Local/Regional* outlets on the one hand and *National* newspapers on the other, between 2014 and 2016, being recorded in the online databases of Europress and Factiva. Depending on the reported newspaper, up to 90% of the articles published online were also published in hard-paper print editions.¹ Using Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods, we construct a weekly dataset at the media level, which reports the salience (share) and tone of immigration-related news articles. We construct two tone measures in the paper that produce very consistent results: Our own man-made measure and an LLM (here ChatGpt) based-measure, both based respectively, on two specific dictionaries of positive and negative words. Using simple econometrics, we then estimate how important terrorism shocks alter the salience and tone of migration coverage and the duration of these shifts overtime.

Our findings indicate that these terrorist attacks triggered media attention on immigration and a marked deterioration in the tone of articles mentioning immigration. Specifically, after a major terrorist event, the words "immigration" or "migration" were more frequently associated with terms like "Muslims" or "(in)security". This resulted in a significant increase in media coverage of these topics, with a multiplication by 5 of our salience measure observed in the first three weeks following an attack across various media outlets. This increase subsequently falls down to around 30-50% in the following weeks, returning to baseline levels about eight weeks after the attack. The shift in tone, while shorter in duration (up to two weeks), was notably severe, with negative tone increasing by almost 100% compared to pre-attack levels. Interestingly, both salience and negative tone shifts were observable in National media outlets, and appear to be rather similar across different political orientations of these media. On the opposite, Regional media behavior towards migration issues changed much less after the attacks.

In the second part of this paper, we investigate how exposure to changes in media behaviour is capable to influence preferences of people and their votes in favor of the main anti-migrant party in France (Far right party). It is plausible that both journalists and the general public were psychologically affected by a significant terrorist event, leading to a statistical correlation between changes in public attitudes toward migrants and changes in media coverage. However,

¹See https://www.discoverfrance.net/France/DF_media.shtml.

this paper aims to establish a direct causal relationship, demonstrating how exposure to media coverage influences people’s voting behavior, beyond any direct psychological effects of the terrorist shock itself.

To explore this, we identify an election which date follows rather closely one of our major terrorist events. Namely, the *Élections Régionales*, a nationwide election was held at the municipal level on December 6, 2015, approximately three weeks after November 13. We use data on the market shares of media outlets at a local level (*Départements* in French) to construct a weighted average exposure measure that varies across French *Départements*². This cross-local variation in media exposure was tested as a determinant of differences in voting outcomes across municipalities using a shift-share research design. As it will be made clearer in the heart of the paper, our shift-share strategy focuses in particular, on the cross-local variation of exposure to *National* media, that we argue to be exogenous to the votes at the municipality level.

Our results show that people more exposed to media concerns about migration (through media salience, negative tone or a mix of both) are more likely to vote for the main anti-migrant party in France at the municipal level. We estimate the contribution of the change in media behaviour to the overall increase in votes for the far right of about 2% on average. However, we estimate this contribution to be at least as high as 12% in some French locations.

We contribute to four strands of literature. First, the political science literature has shown that media often focus disproportionately on specific migrant groups, frequently portraying them negatively. For example, the intensity of media reporting on minorities often does not reflect their actual demographic presence, as is the case with refugees, who are often overrepresented in media coverage compared to their share of migration statistics (Ter Wal, 2002; Lubbers et al., 1998; Blinder and Allen, 2016). When differentiating migrants by religion, Muslim immigrants are the most prominent group in media coverage (Moore et al., 2008), and in the U.S., Latino migrants receive the most negative coverage (Valentino et al., 2013). Media visibility of immigration has been shown to increase public anti-immigration attitudes (Van Klinger et al., 2015; Benesch et al., 2019). In the context of France, Schneider-

²A *Département* in France is an administrative denomination representing a group of municipalities located in a same geographical area.

[Strawczynski and Valette \(2024\)](#) finds that immigration news polarizes attitudes, while other research shows that media coverage of the refugee crisis strengthens Euroscepticism ([Harteveld et al., 2018](#)).

Second, the literature on crime shocks and attitudes towards migrants shows that when the foreign origin of offenders is highlighted, public attitudes and policies towards migrants become more negative. [Couttenier et al. \(2021\)](#) find that increased reporting on crimes committed by foreigners boosts anti-Muslim votes in Switzerland. Conversely, [Keita et al. \(2023\)](#) find that highlighting the native origin of criminals reduces public concerns about immigration. [Djourelova \(2023\)](#) shows that newspapers avoiding the term "illegal immigrant" lead to less support for restrictive immigration policies.

Third, a growing body of research explores the relationship between terrorism and attitudes toward migrants. Some early studies focused on single-country cases, while more recent work uses cross-country surveys (see [Legewie \(2013\)](#), [Schüller \(2015\)](#), [Castanho Silva \(2018\)](#) and [Ferrín et al. \(2020\)](#)). The evidence is mixed: negative shifts in attitudes are not always observed. However, [Ferrín et al. \(2020\)](#) find that the Bataclan attack had a negative impact on attitudes toward immigrants, particularly among educated and left-wing individuals in France.³

Finally, a limited number of economic studies examine the relationship between terrorism and voting behavior. [Montalvo \(2011\)](#) conducts a natural experiment on the 2004 Madrid bombings where he finds that the attacks led to a clear shift in votes against the incumbent party, which had supported the Iraq war. [Balcells and Torrats-Espinosa \(2018\)](#) studies voting behavior after ETA attacks in the Basque region and finds an increase in voter participation but no significant shift in support for the incumbent party. More recently, [Sabet et al. \(2025\)](#) show that right-wing terrorism has contributed to the rise of right-wing populism in Germany. To reach this conclusion, they exploit random variations in successful and failed terrorist attacks in German municipalities. However, all of these studies do not examine explicitly the role of the media in shaping voting behavior towards anti-migrant parties, following terrorist events. Further, no evidence is brought on the extent of the media contribution to the rise of

³Other studies from the Social Identity Theory in social psychology echo the economic studies above (see [Echebarria-Echabe and Fernández-Guede \(2006\)](#) and [Strindberg \(2020\)](#)).

the far-right in recent years.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: In the next section, we present our data and methodology for analyzing the salience and tone of media articles. Section 3 presents our first set of results on the impact of terror shocks on media behavior. In Section 4, we examine how these changes in media behavior influence voting outcomes in favor of anti-migrant parties. Section 5 concludes with a discussion of our findings and avenues for future research.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Media Database

To analyze the discourse on migrants surrounding terrorist attacks, we extracted articles from French local / regional, and national newspapers available on Europress and Factiva. Our focus was on articles published between October 1, 2014 (three months before the Charlie Hebdo attack), and October 31, 2016 (three months after the Nice attack) containing at least one of the terms “immigrant(s),” “migrant(s),” or “migration.”⁴ After removing duplicates, the corpus included 56,697 articles.

Migration related terms might cover a broader scope than the one we are interested in. Articles covering animal, data, geophysical or astronomical related migration, for instance, would be irrelevant to the subject being treated here.

To ensure the relevance of the articles selected so far, we applied the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) technique, a generative probabilistic model that identifies topics within a collection of documents based on word usage patterns (Blei et al., 2003; Jelodar et al., 2019).⁵

After preprocessing (stopword removal and lemmatization using Spacy) and LDA implementation, our LDA technique provided 24 topics. Figure 1 displays the identified topics and the 20 most relevant words for each. Notice that all of these topics appear to be related to human migration issues. Thus, we decided to keep all the articles in our original corpus in the database used in the rest of the paper.⁶ Note that a proportion of 75.2% of our articles come

⁴In French: “immigré(s),” “migrant(s),” or “immigration.”

⁵See Heidenreich et al. (2019) for another application of LDA in media analysis on migration.

⁶Some might consider topics 10 and 17 -both being related to entertainment subjects (e.g., “theater/movie” or “sports/club”)- or topic 19 -related to “religious/christian-related” themes- not to be relevant enough because

from local newspapers and the remaining 24.8% are obtained from national newspapers.

2.2 Measuring Media Saliency

First, we focus our attention on the relative importance of immigration in the media landscape by measuring the saliency of immigration news in the French media. The saliency of migration in a given media (a typical journal) can be simply measured in terms of counts of articles mentioning migration. It can also be expressed in terms of shares, where the share measures the ratio of the former (article counts) to the total number of articles published by the journals at a given point in time (Boomgaarden et al., 2010).

Figure 2a shows, each week, a simple measure of immigration saliency by counting all published articles in France mentioning migration. Figure 2b presents an alternative figure of saliency in terms of *shares*, where the number of articles related to migration in a week is divided by the total number of articles published by all of these journals in a week. Probably because the denominator varies very little overtime, the evolution of the two measures happen to be very similar, both showing strong variation in media attention to the issue of immigration over time, with immigration saliency reaching the highest levels around August-September 2015. These two months concern indeed the European refugees' crisis when European countries, and especially Germany, received more than 1.2 million asylum applications according to Eurostat. The peak of our share and count measures also corresponds to the death of Aylan Kurdi reported on 2 september 2015, the two years old boy refugee whose image made most of the media headlines at that time. Note however that these figures do not change much after the main attacks we are concerned with: as one can see, a slight increase in media attention to immigration follows the shooting of Charlie Hebdo on January 7, 2015, and the November 13, 2015 attack in Paris. The increase in media attention following the Nice attack on July 14, 2016, is not directly observable.

Nevertheless, when we investigate the saliency of articles mentioning together the words "immigration/migration" and "islam/muslims" (not to be confounded with islamism/islamsits), they might not be treating the interrelations between migration and political, social or economic related issues. A closer manual inspection revealed that these topics could still be pertinent to consider. Alternatively however, we have also made further robustness checks where we found that our results were not sensitive to the exclusion of these topics.

the figures change dramatically. From Figure 2c, we observe that, following each of the three terrorist attacks, there is significant increase in news articles discussing simultaneously immigration and Muslims. From a count of around 10 to 20 articles related to both family of words before Charli Hebdo attack, the count headed to more than 100 articles the week after the attack, then stagnated at an average of 25 to 30 article several weeks after the attack. The attack of November 13, 2015 generated again, a significant reaction from the media in terms of salience of news articles citing immigration and Muslims related words, with tendencies reaching back the same levels than those before november 13, few weeks later. Interestingly, although the media reacted to Nice's attack too, the magnitude of that reaction appeared to be smaller.

Figure 2: Saliency of Immigration and Islam-Related News in French Newspapers

(a) Saliency of Immigration news as count

(b) Saliency of Immigration News as Percentage of All News

(c) Saliency of Immigration + Muslims as count

(d) Saliency of Immigration + Muslims as Percentage of All News

Notes: Blue line is our measure of weekly saliency score $Saliency_{w,t}$. Vertical red dashed lines indicate the date of the three major terrorist attacks.

2.3 Measuring Media Tone

Second, and in addition to the salience of migration in newspapers, the way articles discuss such topic is of outmost importance. To identify the tone of articles on immigration, we used a Dictionary-based approach with a list of positive and a list of negative words. We count the occurrences of these positive and negative words, then compute the relative difference between them at the article level. The $Tone_{i,w}$ of each article i , published in week w , is then given by:

$$Tone_{i,w} = \frac{W_{i,w}^P - W_{i,w}^N}{W_{i,w}^T} \quad (1)$$

where $W_{i,w}^P$ is the number of positive words, $W_{i,w}^N$ the number of negative words and $W_{i,w}^T$ is the total number of words, within an article i and a given week w . This measure provides a score that lies between -1 and +1 (Lawlor, 2015).

By construction, such measure does not discriminate between the journalist’s view and influential people’s view being referred to in the paper. For instance, in a far-right journal, one would expect a negative tone towards migrants, whereby the journalist presents the view of a politician as a support to his own sentiment. In a centre or left-wing journal, a journalist might still evoke a politician which has negative attitude about migrants but could still soften (or even contradicts) the politician discourse through the use of some counter-arguments. What is important then is whether or not this measure is likely to capture the general tone of the article written by the journalist. We discuss this point in the next subsection.

Focusing on our *Tone* measure in Equation 1, some issues might arise regarding the right dictionary to use. Which words should be included in this dictionary? Which should be chosen to have positive connotations? Which could be associated with negative connotations? We discuss and analyze three options. A first option is to pick a dictionary in the french language, publicly available. A second option is to build our own dictionary, due to the specific features of immigration related subjects, and the contextual words being used then. A third option is to let an artificial intelligence do it on our behalf.

2.3.1 Publicly available french dictionary

Very few dictionaries are publicly available for tone analysis of the French language. To our knowledge, the only available dictionaries for tone assessment of French news articles are the French translation of two dictionaries developed primarily for the English language. The first is the Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC, [Piolat et al. \(2011\)](#)) dictionary. It focuses on words with psychological meaning. The second is the Lexicoder Sentiment Dictionary (LSDFr [Duval and Pétry \(2016\)](#)), designed to differentiate between the negative and positive tone in a political text. Neither of them were specifically designed for immigration-related texts, however. Rather they were built for political texts in the general sense, including economics, crime, foreign affairs, environment-related texts, etc.

We begin by constructing a *Tone* measure based on the LSDFr dictionary mentioned above that we then apply to our 56,000 articles in our database. ⁷

To validate this dictionary in our context and the *Tone* measure on which it is based, we picked randomly 200 articles (that we shall refer to them as validation series articles or 'V-series' articles) and distributed them among us 4 co-authors. We read carefully each of these V-series articles (with the publishing journal name hidden to ensure unbiased scoring). We then classified each article in function of our own perception (i.e. *subjective* appreciation) of the dominant tone that comes out from each article: a positive, neutral, or negative dominant tone. At the end of the process, 43.4% of articles were classified as having a general negative dominant tone, 31.6% as being rather neutral, and 25% to be associated with a general positive dominant tone. Figure 27 in the appendix shows the distribution of net tone scores based on LSDFr dictionary, across our three different subjective perceptions. The net tone based on the LSDFr dictionary showed limited coherence with our perceptions. It tended to be negatively biased across the three possible dominant outcomes. The distributions did not change much across the three perceptions, while they were expected to shift upward when turning from a negative dominant perception to a neutral one, and again further upward when turning from a neutral perception to a positive dominant perception.

This disappointing outcome can be explained by the idea that such a general dictionary, is not specific to the context being under study. Words can have different inclinations depending

⁷LIWC was not tested due to its cost of purchase and its focus on non-political texts.

on the context (Loughran and McDonald, 2011). For example, the widely used Harvard psycho-sociological dictionary can be ill-suited for financial applications (Gentzkow et al., 2019). Another example, applied to our case of immigration is the word “security”, considered to be positive in general, including within dictionaries with a larger scope such as the LSDFr. We have conducted a context analysis through reading randomly articles referring to the word *security* in our context which revealed that *security* has a negative connotation when used in the context of immigrants. The word is principally used to point out to security concerns which are raised by immigrants. Additionally, for a dictionary to work well, the classification of the words must closely align with how the words are used in a particular context. If a dictionary is developed for a specific application, then this assumption should be easy to justify. But when dictionaries are created for a larger scope, this assumption becomes difficult to justify (Grimmer and Stewart, 2013).

Given the lack of a suitable dictionary for the tone analysis of immigration news in french and to avoid potential miss-classification, we then propose to create a problem-specific dictionary. Our aim is to capture the definitive meaning of words therefore, following Young and Soroka (2012).

2.3.2 Human-based, context-specific, dictionary

To build our own dictionary, we select randomly 200 new articles from the corpus. We refer to these articles as A-series articles in what follows. Our objective is still to identify and categorize words with positive or negative connotations. Our hypothesis is that words that would appear out of these 200 articles to have positive or negative connotations in our view, are representative of the words that should be retrieved in the rest of the nearly 56,300 articles at hand related to immigration. Based on this assumption, we can then compute a new net *Tone* measure using Equation 1 above, for each and every article in our database.

Going back to the choice of our words to be included in the dictionary, the 200 articles that constitute our A-series, were equally and randomly distributed among the four of us (i.e. co-authors and coders). Through our reading, a word was included in our dictionary if at least three coders classified it as positive or negative. For ‘positive’ or ‘negative’ words classified by fewer than three coders, we employed additional strategies. First, we examined different

uses of the word in the corpus, reviewing at least 10 and up to 30 instances if necessary. The final decision regarding the word’s classification was made through team meetings. Words with multiple meanings or tricky contextual usage were excluded from the dictionary.

We accounted for basic negation patterns and word boosters that modify or amplify the meaning of certain words. When a positive word in our dictionary is preceded by a negation,⁸ its score is multiplied by -1, reversing its connotation, and vice versa. We also included boosters: when one of the words in our dictionary is preceded by an amplifier,⁹ its score is multiplied by two. The final dictionary is available in Appendix C and is composed of 1504 words, with 517 positive words and 987 negative words (90% more negative than positive ones). It is not *not* quite unusual to have lexicons exhibiting a high ratio in favor of negative words. After consulting an AI (in this case, ChatGPT) to extract figures from the respective lexicon sources, we find that the Lexicoder Sentiment Dictionary contains 66% more negative words than positive ones, while the Harvard General Inquirer lexicon (in English) shows a nearly 2:1 ratio in favor of negative words.

To validate our dictionary and new *Tone* measure, we compared the outcomes through the use of this measure to the overall perceptions of the coders. One simple way was to go back again to the 200 V-series articles (see above sub-section), and confront the already existing appreciation of the coders (positive, neutral or negative dominant tone for each article) to our new dictionary-based *Tone* measure.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of net tone scores across the three different subjective perceptions of the coders. Our dictionary performed very well, accurately distinguishing between articles with different tones. A very high proportion of articles measured as negative in net by our dictionary were actually already perceived as negative by our own readings, articles we perceived as neutral had their net tone measure lying mostly around 0, and positively

⁸List of negative terms: pas, ne, n’, jamais, plus, rien, aucunement, nullement, sans.

⁹List of amplifiers: absolument, archi, beaucoup, bigrement, bougrement, carrément, complètement, considérablement, cruellement, davantage, diablement, diantrement, divinement, drôlement, entièrement, exceptionnellement, excessivement, extrêmement, fabuleusement, grandement, hyper, impeccablement, incroyablement, infiniment, joliment, merveilleusement, prodigieusement, profondément, rudement, sacrément, spécialement, sublimement, superbement, tellement, terriblement, totalement, trop, très, ultra, vachement, vraiment, énormément.

Figure 3: Author’s Dictionary Validation by Themselves

perceived articles by our readings received mostly positive scores by the net tone measure based on our dictionary.

2.3.3 Machine-based dictionary

Some might argue that our choice of positive or negative words in an article, or our perception of the general tone of an article as researchers, might be different from those of a representative journalist writing his or her article. We thus proceeded by constructing an alternative dictionary using GPT-3.5 Turbo (ChatGPT), a popular large language model developed by OpenAI. We used ChatGPT to classify words with positive or negative connotations in the same 200 A-series articles originally given to human coders.¹⁰ From there, we then constructed an alternative measure of tone using Equation 1, with positive and negative words returned by the machine classification instead of our own (human-based) classification. Figure 23 in the appendix reproduces Figure 3, with the measure of net tone now based on the Machine-based dictionary. The two figures, the one based on machine tone scores and the figure based on our own dictionary, appear to be very much consistent.

¹⁰We used the following prompt to get the list of positive and negative words: *I will provide you with a news article about IMMIGRATION. Your task is to read the article and identify all the words that, in your opinion, have a positive or negative connotation. The goal is to identify and classify each word that could help determine the tone of the article. Therefore, you should return two lists of words (positive and negative words from the text).*

As an ultimate cross-check, we considered again the 200 V-series articles and let now ChatGPT give its own perception about the dominant tone of each of these. Namely, we used it to classify these articles as positive, neutral, or negative based on their *dominant* tone.¹¹ We then compared the tone of articles annotated by human readers with the measure delivered through the ChatGPT-constructed dictionary. Figure 24 in the Appendix shows the result. Our hand-coded measure appears to be very consistent, again, with the general tone returned by ChatGPT.

2.3.4 Figures for the Tone measure

In the rest of the paper, we show the results related to our own-based dictionary. It will be our measure of reference throughout the paper. We use, alternatively, the ChatGPT based dictionary as a robustness check (mainly in Section 4) providing very similar results.

We begin by computing a weekly average tone score $Tone_w$ as follows:

$$Tone_w = \frac{\sum_i Tone_{i,w}}{N_w^M} \quad (2)$$

where N_w^M is the total number of news articles about immigration published in week w and $Tone_{i,w}$ is the tone score of an article i related to migration published during week w , computed using Equation 1. We also compute a by-journal measure, based on the same equation. In Figure 4, we show our measures of average weekly tone about immigration and in Figure 5, we also plot measures of average weekly tone on immigration referring also to Muslims (the measures are computed here over all journals in our database). Both figures show that the tone of immigration-related news varies significantly from one week to another with many of the important dips coinciding with weeks of terrorist attacks. Both measure are volatile.¹²

¹¹The prompt used to classify the news articles for the validation task was: *Determine the overall tone of the following article in relation to the issue of migrants. Possible tones: Positive, Neutral, or Negative. Important Instructions: The tone should be a composite measure based on: (A) The relative negativity or positivity of the actual events or issues covered in the article (50%). (B) The newspaper’s opinions or stance on these events and issues (50%). Justification: Provide a detailed justification for your choice, addressing both (A) and (B) specifically.*

¹²Very similar figures, available upon request, are obtained with the ChatGPT based dictionary.

Figure 4: Mean Tone of Immigration news

Notes : Blue line is our measures of average weekly tone of news articles about immigration from Equation 2. The red dotted line is a weekly moving average. Vertical red dashed lines indicate the date of the three major terrorist attacks within the time frame of the study.

Figure 5: Mean Tone of Immigration + Muslims news

Notes : Blue line is our measures of average weekly tone of news articles about immigration and Muslims from Equation 2. The red dotted line is a weekly moving average. Vertical red dashed lines indicate the date of the three major terrorist attacks within the time frame of the study.

Surprisingly, in contrast to previous findings claiming that news about immigration are generally negative, our data from figure 4 shows that news about general immigration are not negative in general. To the contrary, they appear to be much more frequently positive and, only occasionally negative. On average, the value of the average weekly tone appears to be around 0.015. Besides, the number of positive words appears to be exceeding that of negative ones by 1.5 percent on average during the period.¹³ Figure 4 still shows that the tone related to immigration *in general* is being dramatically deteriorated after our three major shocks.

From Figure 5, we observe that the news discussing immigration while linking it to Muslims is around 0 before Charlie's events and become rather negative on average after Charlie's events. One needs to wait for the end of the period of terrorism in France (after Nice events) to see a sort of recovery trend, again towards an average value a slightly higher than 0, for the last months of observations in our data. That being said, compared to the salience measure where peaks are being observed in the presence of the terror shocks, the dramatic decrease in the net tone does not seem to be observed in the same proportions when articles refer to

¹³For a text of 1000 words say, one would observe 15 more positive words than negative ones related to the subject of immigration.

Muslims (compare Figure 5 to 2c).

Tone might be very heterogeneous across journals of different political orientations, however. This is discussed in what follows.

2.4 Saliency, Tone and Political orientation

Further, we look at how saliency of immigration in the media and the tone towards immigration have been changing across the journals' political orientations. To simplify, we consider two periods: a period before the beginning of the terror wave (Sept.2014-Dec.2014) and a period after the beginning of the terror wave encompassing the three major terror acts and many other smaller scale acts and threat related to terror (Jan.2015- Dec.2016).

We have access to Regional and National Press journals. We use the classification issued by the main political science institution in France (SciencePo) informing about the political orientation of each National Press journal. We group them across three groups: Right leaning, Centre and Left-leaning journals.¹⁴ The rest of the journals not classified by SciencePo, happen to be exclusively Regional Press journals, and were grouped into a fourth heterogeneous category (Regional media).

We first look at the National Press. We examine whether one can find a pattern in the saliency and tone data related to immigration across the three political orientations of these journals. Figures 6a and 6b show the results. When concentrating on the saliency measure (Fig. 6a), it seems that the left leaning journals talk more about immigration than the rest, and even more so during the period of terror. Also, one can identify a U-shaped curve across the three political orientations, where left and right leaning journals talk more about migration while the centre evokes less the migration subject than the rest. This is true whether we look at the period before or whether we concentrate on the period during which terrorist events were active.

From Figure 6b, one can see however that a pattern emerges with respect to the tone scores across different orientations: for either periods, the right-oriented media expresses the

¹⁴The right oriented journals include together far right and traditional right/conservative related media journals (Valeurs actuelles, Le Figaro, Le Point and l'Express). The left oriented group includes the left and far-left related journals (La Croix, Libération, l'Humanité).

least positive tone about immigration, while the left expresses the most positive one. Besides, during the period of terror the tone becomes less positive across all three politically related group categories, with still the same ranking across the 3 categories.

Now, let us turn to articles combining migration with Muslims. Again, one can observe a U-shaped picture for the salience measure: nevertheless, the U-shape is biased to the right as the right-leaning media seems to evoke quite more Muslims when they write about migrants and even more so during the terror period (see figures 6c). Nonetheless, when one turns to the tone variable in figure 6d, that one adopted by the right leaning media, while being the most negative before the terror period across the three orientations, happens to become less negative during the terror wave. This less negative tone during the terror period, is actually remarkable across all three National orientation media. It is even reverted, turning to positive values for the left leaning media, during the terror period. This is consistent with a situation where the media does not want to stigmatize Muslims during a very sensitive period and prefers talking more about muslims without necessarily expressing a more negative sentiment towards this muslim minorities, compared to what these usually do in normal time.

Figures 20a to 20d in the appendix retrace the same series of figures with the three main orientations replaced by each specific journal. Here, similar tendencies are being observed across political orientations. One interesting thing to add here though is that the figures related to the right in the figures 6a to 6d are mostly driven by one newspaper, Valeurs Actuelles, the far right media in France. Also, on the other other extreme, the centre-left and Christian journal (La Croix) is the journal adopting the more positive tone over the migrant community when associated with Muslims.

Second, let us now turn to the Regional Press. Here, the local media seem to talk much less about immigration than the national politically oriented press (i.e. 3 to 5 times less than the left or the right oriented National media). And when it does, it covers the immigration subjects with an even more positive tone than the left-leaning media (ie. see Figures 6a and 6b respectively). Maybe this is because the Regional Press, at least in France, is less politically oriented than the national one in general.

The Regional Press talks even more rarely about the combined subjects of Muslims and immigration together (i.e. the share of news related to those mixed subjects is about 15 times

lower than the one associated with the Right leaning media). However, in the rare cases where it does so, its discourse appears to be much more negative on average.¹⁵

The next section discusses all of these changes in media behaviour while controlling for other factors. In particular, we ask whether there is a real change in salience and tone the weeks lying just after a major terror attack, when controlling for other factors, especially when one conditions out each journal's traditional view about migrants in normal times.

¹⁵Note that behind this average negative figure for the Regional Press regarding its discourse on Muslims and migration, hides an important heterogeneity across the different regional newspapers. Data per Regional journal are available upon request.

Figure 6: Mean Salience and Tone of Immigration and Immigration + Muslims News

(a) Share of News References to Immigration (Mean Salience) (b) Mean Tone Score of News References to Immigration

(c) Share of News References to Immigration + Muslims (Mean Salience) (d) Mean Tone Score of News References to Immigration + Muslims

3 The Impact on Media Behavior: Empirical Strategy and Results

In this section, we outline our empirical strategy to estimate the effect of terrorism on both the salience and tone of immigration-related news coverage. We employ a simple least square dummy variables regression with quarterly and journal fixed effects, using the following specification:

$$Y_{jt} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{\omega} \alpha_{\omega} * T_Week(\omega)_t + \zeta X_t + q_t + \eta_j + u_{jt} \quad (3)$$

Where $Y_{j,t}$ represents either media salience (measured as percentage shares) or media tone at the weekly and journal level.¹⁶ In additional specifications, we also explore how media behavior evolves in terms of salience and tone for articles which mention specific terms, such as Muslims, security, the economy, and humanitarian issues.

Our key explanatory variables, $T_Week(\omega)$ are a set of dummy variables associated with each typical week surrounding the three major terrorist attacks under study. We hypothesize that media responses, particularly in salience and tone, will exhibit a stronger change in the immediate aftermath of these attacks, with the effect diminishing over time. Conversely, if the model correctly identifies the shock, we should not observe *a priori*, a significant effect in the weeks just preceding the attacks. To model these temporal dynamics, we introduce a series of weekly dummy variables: three dummies corresponding to the three weeks before each of the attack ($\omega=-1$ to -3) and 8 dummies for the 8 weeks that begin after the attacks. More precisely, we define $\omega = 0$ a dummy for the week of an attack, and a series of seven dummies ($\omega=1$ to 7) for the next seven weeks following it.¹⁷ The α_w are then to be interpreted to affect $Y_{j,t}$ in deviation to its implicit value that would prevail in normal times (i.e., normal times are those calendar times outside the defined window interval, $w \in [-3; +7]$, surrounding

¹⁶Some newspapers are published weekly, requiring the aggregation of salience and tone figures at the weekly level for daily newspapers.

¹⁷Recall again that we are concentrating here on the 3 major attacks in France. Thus, we implicitly hypothesize that the effect of the attack is homogeneous in the three attacks. We have run regressions based on each of the attacks and found coefficients somewhat quantitatively similar in signs and magnitudes, when one accounts for standard deviations. This is shown in the Appendix.

the attacks).

In addition, X_t represents a set of control variables, including a dummy variable which captures the refugee crisis period (August to September 2015 (peak of the crisis) that we shall call $Ref.Crises_t$, and a $Naufrage_t$ variable dummy indicating the weeks where all majors shipwrecks have occurred during the whole period of our study. Finally, a couple of week-specific dummies related to discovering Aylan Kurdi's body on the Mediterranean coast were introduced. These flag the week of discovery and the week after.¹⁸ In fact, we expect an additional interest in migration and refugees' related issues due to this shocking event. Finally, we include quarterly fixed effects, q_t and journal fixed effects, η_j to account for temporal and publication-specific variations.

3.1 Media Behavior: Results

3.1.1 Saliency

We begin by considering all journals, Regional and National ones. Table 1, presents the results related to the saliency measure. Its main findings are visually represented in Figure 7. Column 1 in the table shows that in the weeks following one of the three major terrorist attacks, there is no statistically significant increase in general immigration coverage in the media. None of the weeks from 0 to 7 show a significant effect on overall immigration coverage.

However, when immigration topics are associated with Muslims (column 2) and (in)security-related words (column 3), a clear pattern emerges. Specifically, the proportion of articles linking immigration with Muslims and security concerns increases significantly. Column 2 reports that in the week of a major terrorist attack, the share of news articles connecting immigration with Muslims rises by approximately 0.14 percentage points. This increase persists, reaching 0.39 percentage points in the second week and 0.25 percentage points in the third week. On average, over the first three weeks, there is an increase of around 0.26 percentage points. After this period, the effect gradually diminishes and disappears by the eighth week.

The magnitude of this effect is substantial. To grasp its significance, it is essential to understand that prior to the terrorism period in France (up to December 2014), the average

¹⁸Basically, in 2015 those dummies turn from 0 to 1 only on the weeks of 31st August to 6th of September, and 7th to 13th of September.

salience of immigration articles referencing Muslims was around 0.07% per journal. This translates to roughly 1 article per 1,400 being published weekly on migration and Muslim-related issues. A major terrorist attack, however, raises this figure by an average of 0.26 percentage points in the first three weeks, increasing the salience from 0.07% to 0.34%. In other words, in the immediate aftermath of a major terrorist attack, approximately 3.4 out of every 1,000 articles per journal are estimated to refer to migration and Muslim-related topics, multiplying the number of such articles by almost five.

A similar pattern is observed in the salience of migration and security-related issues (column 3), with a significant increase lasting up to four weeks after the shock. The magnitude of this effect is comparable to that found in column 2. However, unlike Muslim-related topics, where salience returns to pre-attack levels after eight weeks, the salience of security-related topics returns to normal by the fifth week, with statistical insignificance observed from Week 5 onwards.

Finally, when examining the salience of articles linking migration to economic conditions (column 4) or humanitarian issues (column 5), no significant changes are found in the weeks following a major terrorist attack.

In conclusion, immigration *per se* does not become a prominent subject in the aftermath of a major attack. However, specific themes related to Muslims and security issues in the context of immigration become highly salient, with these effects lasting for approximately 5 to 8 weeks following the attack.

Table 1: Weekly estimates on Salience

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	Percentage.Articles				
	Immigration	Muslims	Security	Economy	Humanitarian
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Minus3	0.19** (0.08)	-0.03 (0.05)	0.08 (0.06)	0.04 (0.04)	0.04* (0.02)
Minus2	0.37*** (0.11)	-0.01 (0.01)	0.02 (0.06)	0.21** (0.10)	0.03 (0.02)
Minus1	0.21** (0.10)	0.05 (0.05)	0.01 (0.04)	0.08 (0.07)	0.05* (0.03)
Week0	0.14 (0.09)	0.14*** (0.04)	0.18** (0.07)	-0.07** (0.03)	-0.02 (0.03)
Week1	0.15 (0.11)	0.39** (0.18)	0.39** (0.15)	-0.08 (0.05)	0.01 (0.03)
Week2	-0.04 (0.08)	0.25 (0.17)	0.23 (0.14)	-0.05* (0.03)	-0.04** (0.02)
Week3	-0.09 (0.08)	0.14** (0.07)	0.12 (0.08)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.05* (0.03)
Week4	0.14 (0.10)	0.19** (0.10)	0.16 (0.10)	0.10** (0.05)	-0.08*** (0.02)
Week5	-0.06 (0.05)	0.10* (0.05)	-0.02 (0.07)	0.02 (0.05)	-0.02 (0.01)
Week6	0.15 (0.15)	0.11** (0.05)	0.02 (0.03)	-0.08* (0.05)	0.01 (0.03)
Week7	-0.16* (0.09)	0.08** (0.04)	-0.07 (0.05)	-0.04 (0.04)	-0.06 (0.04)
Naufrage_day	-0.11 (0.10)	-0.08 (0.06)	-0.09 (0.07)	-0.05* (0.03)	-0.04** (0.02)
refugee_crisis	0.72*** (0.20)	0.10 (0.08)	0.30*** (0.09)	0.22** (0.11)	0.35*** (0.10)
Aylan_Kurdi_Week0	1.37*** (0.33)	0.05* (0.03)	0.53*** (0.18)	0.17 (0.15)	1.03*** (0.23)
Aylan_Kurdi_Week1	1.20*** (0.27)	0.01 (0.03)	0.30** (0.13)	0.17 (0.14)	1.01*** (0.30)
Constant	0.89*** (0.03)	0.02** (0.01)	0.20*** (0.02)	0.31*** (0.02)	0.17*** (0.01)
Observations	3,952	3,432	3,640	3,848	3,848
R ²	0.70	0.57	0.66	0.54	0.36
Adjusted R ²	0.69	0.57	0.65	0.53	0.35

Notes: This table presents the estimates from regressing the immigration salienc measure on a set of pre- and post-terror weekly event indicators. In column 1, the exposure index refers to general immigration coverage in the media. In column 2, the exposure index refers to journal articles where immigration topics are associated with Muslims, and in column 3, where it is related to (in)security. In columns 4 and 5, the exposure index refers to journal articles addressing humanitarian and economic aspects, respectively. All regressions include quarter and year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the journal level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

Figure 7: Weekly Saliency Point Estimate with 90% CI

3.1.2 Tone

An increase in the volume of discourse about migrants and Muslims does not necessarily imply a negative tone. In fact, some media outlets might discuss migrants in a more positive light, emphasizing that they should not be conflated with perpetrators of violence. To provide a comprehensive understanding of media behavior following terrorist attacks, it is essential to examine changes in the tone of coverage, particularly regarding Muslims, within the corpus under analysis.

Figure 8: Weekly Tone Point Estimate with 90% CI

Table 2: Weekly estimates - Tone

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	Media_Tone				
	Immigration	Muslims	Security	Economy	Humanitarian
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Minus3	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.0002 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.004** (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)
Minus2	0.01*** (0.002)	-0.001 (0.001)	0.01* (0.003)	0.004* (0.003)	0.01** (0.003)
Minus1	-0.005*** (0.002)	0.0004 (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)
Week0	-0.005*** (0.001)	-0.01*** (0.001)	-0.01*** (0.002)	-0.005*** (0.001)	-0.01*** (0.002)
Week1	-0.003* (0.002)	-0.003 (0.002)	-0.004*** (0.001)	0.0004 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)
Week2	-0.004** (0.002)	0.0000 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	0.0002 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)
Week3	-0.002 (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)	-0.0001 (0.002)	-0.0003 (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)
Week4	-0.001 (0.002)	0.003* (0.002)	0.004** (0.002)	-0.003* (0.002)	-0.0001 (0.003)
Week5	-0.003** (0.001)	0.0003 (0.002)	0.0002 (0.002)	0.004* (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)
Week6	0.0004 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.003)
Week7	-0.003* (0.002)	0.002 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.003** (0.002)	0.002 (0.002)
Naufrage_day	-0.01*** (0.001)	0.0001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.0005 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.002)
refugee_crisis	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.002* (0.001)	-0.001 (0.002)	0.003** (0.001)	-0.0005 (0.002)
Aylan_Kurdi.Week0	0.02*** (0.003)	0.01*** (0.003)	0.01*** (0.003)	0.01*** (0.003)	0.02*** (0.004)
Aylan_Kurdi.Week1	0.01*** (0.003)	0.01** (0.004)	0.01*** (0.003)	0.01*** (0.003)	0.01*** (0.003)
Constant	0.01*** (0.001)	0.001* (0.001)	0.004*** (0.001)	0.01*** (0.001)	0.002* (0.001)
Observations	4,028	3,498	3,710	3,922	3,922
R ²	0.27	0.06	0.12	0.18	0.21
Adjusted R ²	0.26	0.04	0.11	0.17	0.20

Notes: This table presents the estimates from regressing the immigration Tone measure on a set of pre- and post-terror weekly event indicators. In column 1, the exposure index refers to general immigration coverage in the media. In column 2, the exposure index refers to journal articles where immigration topics are associated with Muslims, and in column 3, where it is related to (in)security. In columns 4 and 5, the exposure index refers to journal articles addressing humanitarian and economic aspects, respectively. All regressions include quarter and year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the journal level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

The results are presented in Table 2 and are more clearly synthesized in Figure 8. In the first three weeks following an attack (i.e., weeks 0, 1, and 2), column 1 shows that the overall tone of immigration-related news becomes significantly more negative. After this period, media sentiment gradually returns to the baseline levels observed outside the attacks defined period, with the tone becoming statistically insignificant from Week 3 onward.

However, when it comes to discussions involving Muslims or security-related issues (columns 2 and 3 of Table 2), terrorism has a pronounced impact, particularly during Week 0 and Week 1. Whether the media refers to Muslims or security, the shift in sentiment during these two weeks is substantial. Specifically, in Week 0 of the attack, the average tone score drops to -0.01 , a significant decrease from the baseline, where the tone was slightly positive at approximately $+0.001$ before the attack period (as seen in columns 2 and 3 of Table 2).¹⁹ This shift represents a decline in tone exceeding 100%. In Week 1, the tone remains negative, though the reduction is about 30% compared to the baseline. Even when the media discuss economic or humanitarian issues in conjunction with migration, the tone becomes more negative during Week 0. Nonetheless, by Week 3, the tone appears to return to that of normal times, regardless of the subject being discussed alongside migration.

How do these results from Table 2 align with the findings from Table 1? Table 1 demonstrates that the media continues to discuss migrants, Muslims, and security-related issues for up to 7 weeks following an attack. However, the tone of these discussions becomes negative primarily in the two weeks immediately following the attack. By the third week, while the media maintains a negative sentiment toward migration, it no longer emphasizes links to security or religion, focusing instead on migration in a more general term. Again, this is consistent with an hypothesis of non-stigmatization towards the muslim community in times of terror.

We also assessed the impact of each of the three terrorist attacks individually (see Appendix A for detailed results). The outcomes for tone are generally consistent across all three attacks, with a negative shift in tone observed for up to 2 weeks when discussing Muslims and/or security. In terms of salience, however, the effects differ somewhat. Following the first attack, Charlie Hebdo, the media significantly referenced Muslims and security issues for up

¹⁹See also Appendices A.1 and A.2 for average measures of salience and tone before and during the attack periods.

to 7 weeks (as indicated by statistically significant coefficients). For the Bataclan attack, the persistence of these references was shorter, lasting about 3 weeks. In the case of the Nice attack, there is no statistically significant effect related to Muslims or security. Nevertheless, the salience of general immigration-related topics increased for up to 6 weeks following the Nice attack.

3.2 Heterogeneity across National and Regional Media

As already mentioned in the prior section, local media appears to be reluctant to talk about migration issues, most probably because it targets all readers interested in local news, irrespectively of their political orientation. This could incite this press to focus on news that avoids heated debates such as those related to immigration.²⁰

We thus look at our effect of terror on the behaviour of media, by seperating the National from the Regional/Local media subpanels. Tables 3 and 4 (and the corresponding figures 9 and 10 which synthesize their results) present the results for the National media sample. They need then to be compared to those based on the Regional media one, in the Appendix. Strikingly, the impact on salience and tone obtained in the prior subsection where all media outlets have been considered, appears to be driven mainly by the National Media panel. In salience terms, when evoking muslims too, the impact lasts for at least eight weeks and, when evoking security issues, it lasts for at least 5 weeks. The size of the effect needs also to be discussed: if one considers the three weeks (week 0 to week 2) just after the attack, the impact happens to increase the share of writings evoking migration and muslims by an average estimate of 0.92 percentage points. In terms of Tone, clearly here the tone for all five measures, either when migration terms are considered alone, or when they are associated with Muslims, security, the economy or humanitarian issues, deteriorates for at least two weeks; More importantly, the size of these effects is higher on average for all of these measures, in this National media subsample than in the whole subsample.

In the Appendix, we deliver the results for the Regional subsample. From figures 33 and 34, it is striking to see that the point estimates are definitely smaller in size and their statistical

²⁰Notwithstanding, in the rare cases where migration is evoked the tone appears to be more negative in general than that of the National journals, as it was reported earlier.

significance lasts considerably less longer overtime. Namely, if one considers the most affected subsample –immigration and Muslims related issues sample– statistical significance (at the 10% confidence level) is found to last up to 3 weeks at most for Salience and for only one week at most for the tone.

3.2.1 Salience

Figure 9: Weekly Salience Point Estimate for the National Media with 90% CI

3.2.2 Tone

Figure 10: Weekly Tone Point Estimate for the National Media with 90% CI

Table 3: Weekly estimates on Saliency - Only National Media

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	Percentage.Articles				
	Immigration	Muslims	Security	Economy	Humanitarian
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Minus3	0.50*	-0.18	0.33	0.05	0.15**
	(0.26)	(0.20)	(0.27)	(0.16)	(0.06)
Minus2	0.92*	0.01	-0.01	0.87**	0.05
	(0.48)	(0.05)	(0.25)	(0.40)	(0.06)
Minus1	0.76*	0.22	0.02	0.29	0.14*
	(0.43)	(0.20)	(0.13)	(0.31)	(0.08)
Week0	0.42	0.41***	0.59**	-0.22*	-0.05
	(0.34)	(0.13)	(0.24)	(0.12)	(0.10)
Week1	0.64	1.36**	1.42***	-0.22	0.05
	(0.44)	(0.64)	(0.49)	(0.21)	(0.13)
Week2	0.25	0.95	0.85	-0.11	-0.02
	(0.35)	(0.67)	(0.54)	(0.15)	(0.07)
Week3	0.17	0.54**	0.59**	0.14	-0.08
	(0.32)	(0.25)	(0.28)	(0.09)	(0.11)
Week4	0.72**	0.72**	0.64*	0.43**	-0.17***
	(0.37)	(0.35)	(0.38)	(0.20)	(0.03)
Week5	-0.03	0.26**	-0.24	0.12	0.01
	(0.21)	(0.12)	(0.46)	(0.23)	(0.07)
Week6	0.13	0.41**	0.10	-0.22	0.07
	(0.39)	(0.19)	(0.08)	(0.23)	(0.11)
Week7	-0.22	0.33***	-0.15	-0.11	-0.07
	(0.32)	(0.11)	(0.22)	(0.15)	(0.12)
Naufrage_day	0.03	-0.28	-0.10	-0.17**	-0.20***
	(0.47)	(0.29)	(0.25)	(0.07)	(0.06)
refugee_crisis	1.73***	0.37	0.68***	0.50*	0.84***
	(0.59)	(0.31)	(0.22)	(0.25)	(0.25)
Aylan_Kurdi_Week0	3.61***	0.13	1.80***	0.87*	2.36***
	(1.15)	(0.11)	(0.59)	(0.47)	(0.63)
Aylan_Kurdi_Week1	2.68***	0.01	0.85*	0.93**	2.79**
	(0.80)	(0.13)	(0.50)	(0.38)	(1.13)
Constant	3.41***	0.23***	0.91***	0.59***	0.74***
	(0.11)	(0.02)	(0.14)	(0.05)	(0.04)
Observations	832	832	832	832	832
R ²	0.63	0.53	0.58	0.46	0.39
Adjusted R ²	0.61	0.52	0.57	0.44	0.37

Notes: This table presents the estimates from regressing the immigration saliency measure on a set of pre- and post-terror weekly event indicators. In column 1, the exposure index refers to general immigration coverage in the media. In column 2, the exposure index refers to journal articles where immigration topics are associated with Muslims, and in column 3, where it is related to (in)security. In columns 4 and 5, the exposure index refers to journal articles addressing humanitarian and economic aspects, respectively. All regressions include quarter and year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the journal level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 4: Weekly estimates on Tone - Only National Media

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	Media_Tone				
	Immigration	Muslims	Security	Economy	Humanitarian
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Minus3	0.001 (0.001)	0.0003 (0.004)	0.004** (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)
Minus2	0.004** (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	0.01*** (0.003)	0.01* (0.003)	0.001 (0.004)
Minus1	-0.0002 (0.004)	0.0003 (0.01)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.002)
Week0	-0.01*** (0.002)	-0.01*** (0.001)	-0.01*** (0.002)	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.01*** (0.001)
Week1	-0.01*** (0.002)	-0.01** (0.003)	-0.01*** (0.003)	-0.01*** (0.004)	-0.01*** (0.002)
Week2	-0.002 (0.003)	-0.004 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.01** (0.003)	-0.005*** (0.001)
Week3	-0.003 (0.003)	-0.003 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.005* (0.003)	-0.003 (0.002)
Week4	-0.003 (0.002)	0.0003 (0.004)	0.002 (0.003)	-0.003*** (0.001)	-0.001 (0.01)
Week5	0.001 (0.002)	0.003 (0.004)	0.005** (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)	0.004 (0.003)
Week6	-0.002 (0.002)	0.003 (0.003)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	0.001 (0.003)
Week7	-0.001* (0.001)	-0.002 (0.003)	0.001 (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)	0.003 (0.003)
Naufrage_day	-0.003* (0.002)	-0.0002 (0.002)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.01*** (0.002)	-0.01* (0.003)
refugee_crisis	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.0004 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.003)	-0.003* (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)
Alan_Kurdi_Week0	0.01* (0.004)	-0.0001 (0.01)	0.005 (0.004)	0.01*** (0.002)	0.01 (0.01)
Alan_Kurdi_Week1	0.01*** (0.003)	0.001 (0.004)	0.01*** (0.003)	0.01*** (0.002)	0.004 (0.004)
Constant	0.02*** (0.0004)	0.003*** (0.001)	0.004*** (0.001)	0.02*** (0.001)	0.02*** (0.001)
Observations	848	848	848	848	848
R ²	0.24	0.09	0.15	0.13	0.17
Adjusted R ²	0.22	0.06	0.12	0.11	0.15

Notes: This table presents the estimates from regressing the immigration Tone measure on a set of pre- and post-terror weekly event indicators. In column 1, the exposure index refers to general immigration coverage in the media. In column 2, the exposure index refers to journal articles where immigration topics are associated with Muslims, and in column 3, where it is related to (in)security. In columns 4 and 5, the exposure index refers to journal articles addressing humanitarian and economic aspects, respectively. All regressions include quarter and year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the journal level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

In the appendix, we test further for the heterogeneity of our treatment effect across political orientations: interestingly, we find that the effect is rather similar in sign and magnitude across left and right wing newspapers. If anything, the left-wing journals seem to react slightly more than the right-wing ones.

4 Voting Behavior: Empirical Strategy and Results

The objective of this section is to explore how changes in media coverage of migration-related topics following a major terrorist attack can influence voting behavior. Specifically, we are not aiming to show that terrorist events themselves directly change voting patterns. Instead, the focus is on identifying whether increased salience and more negative tones in migration-related news during the weeks after the attacks affect voting outcomes—and if so, by how much?

To isolate this effect on voting outcomes, we needed to identify a French election that occurred within a few weeks of at least one major terrorist attack. Incidentally, an important nationwide election took place in early December 2015: the *Élections Régionales* were held on the 6th and 13th of December. These elections are designed to elect a regional council for each region in France, which is responsible for regional policymaking. Our analysis will focus on the first round of these elections, held on December 6th, where all political parties were represented. Crucially, this date falls in the third week following the November 13th Bataclan attack, which is optimal for our study, as most media change in behaviour tend to occur for 2 to 8 weeks following the attack (as shown in the previous section).

Data on voting outcomes are available at various local levels in France. The challenge here was to link differences in voting outcomes to the varying levels of media exposure across municipalities, while controlling for other factors that could have influenced voting outcomes across these municipalities.

4.1 Vote Shares: Some Facts for France

Data on voting outcomes for the *Élections Régionales* were collected from the official government website, at the municipality level (the "Commune" level).²¹ For comparison purposes and to meet the control requirements for our econometric model presented below, we also collected voting outcomes from the previous *Élections Régionales* which took place in March 2010. The dataset includes outcomes from around 36,000 communes.

Our main objective is to determine whether changes in media reporting influenced voters' preferences for anti-migrant parties following the attacks. In France, one anti-migrant party stands out: the far-right Front National (FN), which was rebranded as Rassemblement National (RN) in 2018. Given its long-standing anti-migrant stance and nationwide presence, our analysis focuses specifically on this party. At the national level, during the December 2015 elections, the FN significantly increased its vote share, which arose from 11.42% in the first round of the 2010 election to 27.73% in 2015— a historical 145% increase, which is the highest observed in local elections in France, for a far-right party.

France is administratively divided into *regions*, which are further divided into *Départements* (which, to some extent, are similar to counties in the U.S.). Each *Département* is made up of several municipalities, or *communes*. Figure 11 displays the average percentage change in FN vote share across 95 French *Départements* between the 2010 and 2015 *Élections Régionales*. In some *Départements*, the FN's vote share increased by more than 300%, particularly in areas where the party previously received minimal support. This demonstrates a "catch-up effect", where regions with initially low FN support in 2010 experienced the largest growth by 2015. This shift in favor of the FN is also observable at the municipal level. Figure 12 shows the distribution of FN votes across all French *communes* in 2010 and 2015. Notably, the entire distribution shifted to the right by 2015, indicating a widespread increase in FN support.

While many factors could explain the rise of the far-right in France, the specific question we ask here is: did the media's communication on immigration following the November 2015 terrorist attacks play a role in the increase in FN support, as illustrated in Figures 11 and 12? We attempt to answer this question in the following analysis.

²¹Website : (data.gouv.fr)

Figure 11: Change in vote share (%) for the FN, at the Département level, between 2010 and 2015

Change in Vote Share for the Far Right from 2010 to 2015 Regional Election

Figure 12: Distribution of the FN Vote share across municipalities, in 2010 and 2015

4.2 Measures of Exposure Related to Migration News

To assess the impact of media exposure on voter behavior, we need data that reflects how much people are exposed to the media outlets in our analysis. The *Alliance pour les Chiffres de la Presse et des Médias* (ACPM) is a well-established institution in France’s media market that provides certified measures of market shares for all French newspapers at the *Département* level.²² Market shares here are defined by shares of circulation of journals: that is, they are based on the total number of hard copy sales and online subscriptions.

Our data on salience and tone related to migration are constructed at the journal level. For each *Département*, where municipalities and their voters are located, we can define a measure of potential exposure to migration-related articles. This measure is a weighted average of salience (or tone) across the journals that people in a given *Département* are exposed to. The weights are based on each journal’s share of circulation in the *Département*. For example, if in a certain *Département*, two journals are sold—one local, accounting for 80% of newspaper circulation, and one national, representing the remaining 20%—then a voter in that *Département* would be potentially exposed to a weighted average of the salience or tone of these articles. In this case, the local journal would weigh four times more heavily than the national journal. Therefore, if the local journal has a negative attitude towards migrants after a terrorist attack, while the national journal maintains a neutral stance, people in that *Département* would be exposed to four times more of the negative tone from the local newspaper than the neutral tone from the national one. Consequently, the overall exposure measure would reflect this imbalance.

It is important to note that allowing journal circulation shares to vary over time would make the exposure measure endogenous by construction. If people’s attitudes towards migrants become more negative after the attack, they might choose to read more from journals that report negatively on migration. This unobservable change in preferences could affect both voting outcomes and the sales of newspapers, potentially biasing the causality on votes we want to identify. To avoid this, we hold the circulation shares at their 2014 levels, just before the wave of terrorist attacks in France began.

Some might argue that it would be more accurate to have market shares data at the mu-

²²In English, this can be translated as *The Alliance for Media and Press Data*.

municipality level rather than the *Département* level. Such information is not available, however. Even if it were, using it might not be ideal, as people commute in general from their home residence (located in some municipality) to major urban centers in the *Département* either for work or to purchase goods and services. Therefore, using *Département*-level newspaper circulation may actually be a more appropriate way to calculate our exposure measures. Notice in passing that sales at the department level are also more likely to be exogenous relative to preference shift observed in a particular municipality.

We are particularly interested in voters' exposure to the salience and tone of journals during the three-weeks that followed the November 13 attacks, which we want to compare to a period of reference that we choose to be the three-weeks period before the attack. Recall that media attitudes towards migration are estimated in the prior section to be similar to normal times in the three weeks leading up to the attack (as indicated by the non-significant parameters for the variables from Weeks -1 to -3 in our earlier salience and tone measures).

Let us define the after-attack period to be called period a and the before attack one to be called period b . Then, in a given period p ($p \in \{a, b\}$), the potential exposure of a voter to media attitudes, measured by say, a variable A , calculated at the *Département* level, is defined as:

$$Expo(A)_m^p = \sum_j c_{m(D),j} \times A_j^p \quad (4)$$

Where A represents our alternative measures of Media *Attitudes*, through our salience or net tone indicators. Thus, A_j^p measures the salience or tone of a journal j 's towards migrants, during a period p , the latter representing either the 3 weeks before the attack ($p = b$) or the 3 weeks after ($p = a$). For each period, we define an average salience measure by aggregating the number of migration-related articles over the three weeks and dividing by the total number of articles published by each journal. Alternatively, the average tone score is calculated by summing the tone scores for all migration-related articles published during the period and dividing by the total number of articles, for each observed journal. Finally, $c_{m(D),j}$ represents the circulation share of journal j in the *Département* D in 2014, where municipality m is located.

From there one can then compute the shift in exposure to media attitudes about migration

after November 13 (compared to the period just before), as:

$$\text{Sh}^{ab} \text{Exp}(A)_m = \text{Exp}(A)_m^a - \text{Exp}(A)_m^b = \sum_j c_{m(D),j} \times \text{Sh}^{ab} A_j \quad (5)$$

4.3 Model specification

We aim to model the change in votes in favor of the main far-right party in December 2015 relatively to previous elections (held in 2010). By expressing the votes in differences, the obtained specification has then the advantage of controlling for unobserved voting factors for the far-right at the municipality level which are invariant between 2010 and 2015. We test whether municipalities being more exposed to the media shift, are more likely to adjust their votes in 2015 in favor of the anti-migrants party, compared to those that prevailed in 2010.

This provides the following equation to test:

$$\Delta \text{Vote}_m = \lambda + \beta \text{Sh}^{ab} \text{Exp}(A)_m + X_m \alpha + v_m \quad (6)$$

Here, $\Delta \text{Vote}_m = \text{Vote}_{m,15} - \text{Vote}_{m,10}$ represents the change in the far-right party's vote share between 2010 and 2015 at the municipal level, expressed in percentage points. The variable A indicates whether the measure used in the regression is salience ($A = S$) or net tone ($A = T$). The parameter β represents the treatment effect on $\text{Sh}^{ab} \text{Exp}(A)_m$ that we aim to identify. The vector, X_m includes control variables that account for various factors expected to influence the change in voting outcomes across municipalities. In particular, at the *Département* level we control for the change in unemployment and GDP (in percentage terms) between 2015 and 2010. At the municipal level, we could include other controls such as crime rates (per 1,000 inhabitants), the share of migrants, the percentage of residents aged 60 and older, and the poverty rates, all observed in 2015.²³

Three additional notes need to be mentioned before proceeding to the results. The first is related to the impact of terrorist attacks, independently of the way they interact with migration issues in the media discourse. Indeed, while the terrorist attacks of 2015 including

²³Unfortunately, we could not obtain data for 2010, to be able to construct variables of differences in these measures between 2015 and 2010. All Data are sourced from the French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE).

that of November 13, might favor the votes in support for the extreme right at the national level, this impact is captured through the shifter term, λ . Empirically, λ is actually estimated by the intercept of our econometric regression and is expected to be positive and statistically significant. Recall again however, that the goal of our analysis in this paper is not to measure the nationwide effect of the attacks *per se*: rather, our objective is to identify how a higher exposure to the media in a municipality, after an attack, influences voting in favor of the anti-migrant party, on the top of the average effect of a nationwide shock being captured by λ .

Second, we exclude municipalities in the $\hat{\text{Île-de-France}}$ region.²⁴ This decision was made because the November 13 attacks had an especially strong impact on both voters and journalists in $\hat{\text{Île-de-France}}$. Including these municipalities might lead to biased estimates of β , as changes in media discourse and voter preferences in $\hat{\text{Île-de-France}}$ could simply reflect simultaneous shifts in both groups, and not necessarily a causality (i.e impact of the media on voting).

Third, recall that our key variable of interest, $\text{Sh}^{ab} \text{Expo}(A)_m$ is computed using *fixed* weights for each journal—specifically, those are being represented by the journals’ circulation share in 2014. In essence, we are conducting a sort of Shift-Share (Bartik) regression (see [Borusyak et al. \(2025\)](#)), where our key variable shifts with the respective changes in local and national media attitudes, weighted each by their market share, observed before the terror wave. In our case, we are more confident in the exogeneity of the share variable (the local distribution of newspaper sales before the attacks period) than in that of the shift (changes in journalistic attitudes and salience of migration averaged across all media outlets). Nevertheless, we will further explore refinements to strengthen the plausibility of the exogeneity of the shift in overall media attitudes by proposing a simple instrument for it.

4.4 First Results

We now present a first set of results from simple linear regressions based on equation 6. Recall that the exposure variables can be expressed in terms of both salience and tone. Additionally,

²⁴We exclude municipalities from the following Départements: Paris (75), Seine-et-Marne (77), Yvelines (78), Essonne (91), Hauts-de-Seine (92), Val-de-Marne (94), and Val-d’Oise (95).

tone can be defined using either our custom dictionary or ChatGPT’s dictionary. This allows us to examine how each of these three exposure variables (salience, own tone measure, and the ChatGPT tone) influence voting outcomes. In the results that follow, the key coefficient to focus on across these variables is the β coefficient from equation 6, which captures the changes in votes in some municipality when more exposed to a change in media behaviour.

Table 5 presents the first set of results. Columns (1) through (3) analyze how votes for the far-right party respond to media coverage of immigration issues, based on the exposure variables. The findings reveal notable differences across the specifications. In column (1), focusing on the salience measure, one observes no statistically significant effect of increased migration reporting on the vote share for the far-right party (FN). In columns (2) and (3), both tone measures indicate that increased exposure to negative media tone following the attack are associated with a rise in far-right voting. This suggests that while the sheer volume of immigration coverage (salience) does not influence voters, the tone of this coverage—whether defined using our dictionary or ChatGPT’s—plays a critical role in shaping electoral outcomes.

In columns (4) through (6), we analyze media exposure specifically related to migrants and Muslims. The results indicate that neither changes in the volume of news coverage on these topics nor shifts in the tone of these articles have a significant impact on voting outcomes. Columns (7) through (9) turn to media exposure that combines discussions of migrants and security-related issues. Column (7) shows that increased exposure to the volume of such articles is associated with a rise in far-right voting, while columns (8) and (9) indicate that heightened exposure to a negative tone in these articles following the attack is also associated with increased far-right support.

4.5 Tackling Endogeneity: Alternative Approaches and Robustness Checks

One important issue we must address is the potential endogeneity of our exposure measures. To begin with, a terrorist attack can shift people’s attitudes making them become more negative about migrants, which may lead them to favor anti-migrant policies, as it can be reflected in their voting behavior (i.e. change in voting preferences). This is favoured by stereotypes, being entertained further by the media (see for instance [Bordalo et al. \(2016\)](#)). Then, endogeneity may arise when media firms, in turn, seeking to maximize their share of

Table 5: Impact of Weighted Exposures to (NATIONAL and REGIONAL) Media on votes

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>								
	Δ_Vote								
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
$\Delta_Salience_Immigration_News$	-3.78 (2.33)								
$\Delta_Tone_Immigration_News$		-2.39*** (0.91)							
$\Delta_Tone_GPT_Immigration_News$			-3.33*** (1.16)						
$\Delta_Salience_Muslims_News$				1.27 (1.86)					
$\Delta_Tone_Muslims_News$					-1.14 (2.47)				
$\Delta_Tone_GPT_Muslims_News$						-4.46 (2.86)			
$\Delta_Salience_Security_News$							3.21** (1.63)		
$\Delta_Tone_Security_News_Nat_Reg$								-2.12** (0.90)	
$\Delta_Tone_GPT_Security_News$									-2.83** (1.20)
CrimeCases_1000hab	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)	-0.03*** (0.01)
Share_Immigrant_Population	-8.09* (4.55)	-6.11 (4.48)	-7.26 (4.55)	-7.72* (4.61)	-7.56 (4.62)	-7.95* (4.58)	-8.50* (4.56)	-8.16* (4.64)	-8.72* (4.59)
$\Delta_Unemployment$	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.001)	-0.002** (0.001)	-0.002*** (0.001)
Δ_GDP	-0.49*** (0.12)	-0.30** (0.13)	-0.27** (0.14)	-0.47*** (0.12)	-0.46*** (0.14)	-0.40*** (0.13)	-0.40*** (0.13)	-0.39*** (0.12)	-0.39*** (0.12)
Share_People_Over_60	-0.18*** (0.02)	-0.16*** (0.02)	-0.16*** (0.02)	-0.18*** (0.02)	-0.18*** (0.02)	-0.18*** (0.02)	-0.18*** (0.02)	-0.17*** (0.02)	-0.17*** (0.02)
Share_Poverty	0.62*** (0.09)	0.63*** (0.09)	0.58*** (0.09)	0.63*** (0.09)	0.62*** (0.09)	0.60*** (0.09)	0.63*** (0.09)	0.56*** (0.09)	0.56*** (0.09)
Constant	20.89*** (2.04)	17.24*** (2.08)	18.59*** (1.97)	20.49*** (2.16)	20.49*** (2.40)	20.27*** (2.09)	19.29*** (2.23)	20.43*** (1.91)	20.69*** (1.90)
Observations	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678
R ²	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18
Adjusted R ²	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18

Notes: This table presents the estimates from regressing the change in voting for the far-right party from 2010 to 2015 on the change in media weighted exposure variable, using the specification in Eq (6). In columns (1) to (3), we examine how votes for the far-right party respond to media reporting on general immigration issues, using a salience-based measure, a custom tone-based measure, and a ChatGPT tone-based measure, respectively. In columns (4) to (6), we focus on media exposure specifically related to migrants and Muslims, using salience-based and the two tone-based measures, respectively. Columns (7) to (9) focus on media exposure to news that combine discussions of migrants and security-related issues, using salience-based and the two tone-based measures, respectively. Standard errors are clustered at the department level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

sales and thus their profits, might anticipate the readers' shift in attitudes and adjust their content accordingly, publishing more articles about migrants that they would mostly write with a more negative tone. If this endogeneity is not properly accounted for, it could bias upward, in absolute value, the estimates of our treatment variable (i.e., the change in exposure after the attack).

But an opposite mechanism can also be at work. Some journals, mainly local ones, have editorial policies that are usually neutral vis-à-vis sensitive matters like immigration. If they are forward looking, they know that in order to maintain their future readers they need not polarize too much the debate about migrants. This behaviour, if relatively general across local journals, could bias downward the effect to be identified.

Now, we cannot observe change in preferences of people after the November 13 attack, neither could we observe media strategies. The challenge, therefore, is to produce unbiased estimates or, at the very least, offer a method to quantify the potential bias caused by unobserved factors. To address this, we implement two strategies. The first involves improving our Shift-Share instrument approach, used in the previous analysis. The second strategy employs a method developed by [Oster \(2019\)](#), which estimates the extent of bias in our parameters due to unobservable factors, such as changes in voter preferences after the November 13th attack, that we cannot directly measure.

4.5.1 Shift-Share Strategy

The use of exposure measures with fixed weights for each journal, as discussed earlier, represents a basic shift-share strategy. However, this strategy may not be sufficient to fully address endogeneity. Again, whether they favor current or future sales, journals should respond to changes in preferences of people either by swimming with the tide or by applying healing strategies.

One way to remove endogeneity is to focus on national media only. National media journals are not neutral, each having in general a well-known political orientation. Besides, National media is produced in the Paris region (more precisely called, Ile de France region). Because November 13 events have been taking place there, those journalists working for these media were probably very much affected (more than the average readers who resides outside

Paris). What is more, as they write to Nationwide readers they do not specifically target one typical locality in France. Hence, they would not adjust the quantity and tone of their articles about migrants with respect to readers of some particular region, as far as localities outside Île-de-France are concerned (i.e. outside all 'Départements' including and surrounding Paris).

As a result, the exposure of people to National media in localities outside Île-de-France is likely to be more exogenous (or at least, much less endogenous) to voting patterns. Hence, since the overall change in media exposure can be decomposed into exposure to National media and exposure to Regional media, we re-apply a shift-share strategy but now through focusing solely on National media.

Table 6 presents the results focusing on National media. Columns (10) through (12) replicate the specifications from columns (1) to (3) of Table 5. The findings are consistent with those in Table 5: the coefficient for salience (column 10) remains statistically insignificant, while the coefficients for tone (columns 11 and 12), measured using both our custom dictionary and ChatGPT's dictionary, are negative and statistically significant. Interestingly, the estimator is now measured to be higher in absolute value than in the prior table. These results suggest rather a downward bias when all media were considered, and thus favor our second explanation: local media may be trying to heal the situation.

Columns (13) through (15) reproduce the specifications from columns (4) to (6) of Table 5, focusing on National media exposure related specifically to migrants and Muslims. Unlike the results in Table 5, column (13) shows that increased salience towards migrant subjects in National media is significantly associated with higher far-right voting. Furthermore, columns (14) and (15) reveal that heightened exposure to a negative tone in these articles following the attack is also linked to increased far-right support.

Finally, columns (16) through (18) replicate the specifications from columns (7) to (9) of Table 5, concentrating on National media exposure that combines discussions of migrants and (in)-security issues. Column (16) indicates that greater exposure to the volume of such news is associated with a rise in far-right voting. Similarly, column (18) shows that more negative tones in these articles (measured using ChatGPT's dictionary) is linked to higher far-right support. However, the tone measure based on our custom dictionary (column 17) is statistically insignificant.

Table 6: Impact of Exposures to NATIONAL Media on votes

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>								
	Δ_Vote								
	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)	(17)	(18)
$\Delta_Salience_Immigration_News_Nat$	-2.15 (7.33)								
$\Delta_Tone_Immigration_News_Nat$		-3.05* (1.64)							
$\Delta_Tone_GPT_Immigration_News_Nat$			-7.35* (4.33)						
$\Delta_Salience_Muslims_News_Nat$				4.29** (2.16)					
$\Delta_Tone_Muslims_News_Nat$					-6.00* (3.32)				
$\Delta_Tone_GPT_Muslims_News_Nat$						-12.58** (6.35)			
$\Delta_Salience_Security_News_Nat$							3.26* (1.69)		
$\Delta_Tone_Security_News_Nat$								-4.35 (2.68)	
$\Delta_Tone_GPT_Security_News_Nat$									-9.22* (5.53)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	20.85*** (2.09)	19.13*** (2.42)	19.24*** (2.45)	19.32*** (2.34)	19.14*** (2.45)	19.05*** (2.41)	19.66*** (2.26)	19.30*** (2.46)	19.24*** (2.47)
Observations	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678
R ²	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17
Adjusted R ²	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17

Notes: This table presents the estimates from regressing the change in voting for the far-right party from 2010 to 2015 on the change in National media exposure, using the specification in Eq (6). In columns (10) to (12), we examine how votes for the far-right party respond to National media reporting on general immigration issues, using a salience-based measure, a custom tone-based measure, and a ChatGPT tone-based measure, respectively. Columns (13) to (15) focus on media exposure to the national media, specifically related to migrants and Muslims, using salience-based and the two tone-based measures, respectively. Columns (16) to (18) focus on media exposure from the national media to news that combine discussions of migrants and security-related issues, using using salience-based and the two tone-based measures, respectively. Standard errors are clustered at the department level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

4.6 Tone-weighted Saliency Measure

So far, we have analyzed the effects of saliency and tone alternatively, not together. This is because both measures are affected by the November 13th shock, which potentially bias the results if they were to be introduced together. To address this, we propose an alternative variable that combines both factors in one take-away variable. We begin by weighting each migration-related article by the inverse of its tone (i.e. $[1/(1 + \textit{Tone})]$), and then sum over those articles for each journal and each given week. This produces what we shall call a Tone-Weighted number of articles evoking migrants, by journal j and for each week of observation w , denoted as, $W_T N_{w,j}^M$. By dividing by the total number of articles published by each journal in each week, we obtain a Tone-Weighted Saliency variable:

$$W_T \textit{Saliency}_{w,j} = \frac{W_T N_{w,j}^M}{N_{w,j}} \quad (7)$$

The tone measure can be negative, but it never drops below -1, ensuring that $1 + \textit{Tone}$ is always greater than 0, making the Tone-Weighted Saliency variable easy to interpret. This variable can be thought to be a proxy for *media concern* about immigration: when a terror shock increases the share of articles with a negative tone, the Tone-Weighted Saliency measure rises. Besides, this variable has the property to be directly comparable to the standard saliency measure. In weeks where all migration-related articles have a neutral tone ($\textit{Tone} = 0$), the Tone-Weighted Saliency is identical to the saliency measure. However, during weeks when the media expresses concern about migration with a negative tone, the Tone-Weighted Saliency will exceed the simple saliency measure. We can then compute exposure to media using this Tone-Weighted Saliency variable.

Table 7 presents the results for the Tone-Weighted Saliency variable, focusing exclusively on National media exposure. Column (19) replicates column (10) from Table 6, showing no significant effect of the standard saliency measure on far-right voting.

Columns (20) and (21) present results for the Tone-Weighted Saliency variable derived from general immigration news, with tone measured using our custom dictionary and ChatGPT's dictionary, respectively. Consistent with earlier findings in Tables 5 and 6, the results indicate that changes in the volume of general immigration news, whether tone-weighted or not, have no significant effect on far-right voting.

Column (22) replicates column (13) from Table 6, while columns (23) and (24) examine the Tone-Weighted Saliency for news specifically about immigrants and Muslims, using tone measures from both dictionaries. The coefficients in columns (23) and (24) align closely with those in column (22) in terms of sign, statistical significance, and magnitude. These results suggest that increased coverage of news about immigrants and Muslims following a terrorist attack—whether tone-weighted or not—is associated with a rise in far-right voting.

Lastly, column (25) replicates column (16) from Table 6, while columns (26) and (27) focus on the Tone-Weighted Saliency for news linking migrants to security concerns, using both tone measures. Again, the coefficients in columns (26) and (27) are consistent with those in column (25) regarding sign, statistical significance, and magnitude. These findings indicate that heightened exposure to news associating migrants with security issues after a terrorist attack is strongly linked to increased support for the far-right.

Further, some might argue that national media are particularly sensitive to the preferences of large urban municipalities, where people are more educated and concerned with national-level issues, leading to a higher share of national media consumption. If this is the case, the results might still be subject to endogeneity between exposure and voting behavior, especially in large cities. In Table 8, we address this concern by reproducing the results from Table 7, but limiting the analysis to small cities (with populations below 2,000). The coefficients in table 8 are consistent with those in table 7 regarding sign and statistical significance. A closer look at standard errors and a simple computation of confidence intervals, shows that the value of the coefficients are of similar magnitude as well.²⁵

To sum-up, what is really affecting people’s vote in favor of the main anti-migrant party in France after November 13, is probably not migrants *per se*. Rather it is the muslim group of migrants in particular that matters. Besides, it is also insecurity related to migration that plays a role. The magnitude of the impact across French regions will be discussed in subsection 4.8.

²⁵The results are not sensitive to the population threshold. Similar results are obtained when using thresholds of 5,000 ; 10,000 or 20,000 inhabitants.

Table 7: Impact of NATIONAL media Concern about migration (Tone-weighted Salience Measure)

	Dependent variable:								
	Δ_Vote								
	(19)	(20)	(21)	(22)	(23)	(24)	(25)	(26)	(27)
Δ_Salience_Immigration_News_Nat	-2.15 (7.33)								
Δ_Salience_Immigration_Tone_Weighted_Nat		1.57 (7.86)							
Δ_Salience_Immigration_Tone_Weighted_GPT_Nat			-0.93 (7.52)						
Δ_Salience_Muslims_News_Nat				4.29** (2.16)					
Δ_Salience_Muslims_Tone_Weighted_Nat					4.19** (2.11)				
Δ_Salience_Muslims_Tone_Weighted_GPT_Nat						4.24** (2.13)			
Δ_Salience_Security_News_Nat							3.26* (1.69)		
Δ_Salience_Security_Tone_Weighted_Nat								3.18* (1.64)	
Δ_Salience_Security_Tone_Weighted_GPT_Nat									3.23* (1.67)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	20.85*** (2.09)	20.91*** (2.08)	20.89*** (2.08)	19.32*** (2.34)	19.32*** (2.34)	19.32*** (2.34)	19.66*** (2.26)	19.64*** (2.26)	19.65*** (2.26)
Observations	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678
R ²	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17
Adjusted R ²	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17

Notes: This table presents the estimates from regressing the change in voting for the far-right party from 2010 to 2015 on the change in National media exposure, using the specification in Eq (6). In columns (19, 22 and 25) we examine how votes for the far-right party respond to National media reporting on immigration issues, using a salience-based measure of Immigration news, and a salience-based measure of news related to both migrants and Muslims, as well as news discussing both immigrants and security related issues respectively. In columns (20 and 21), we replace the salience based measure in column (19) by *media concern* measure constructed using Eq. (7), with tone measured by our custom dictionary in column (20) and by ChatPGT in column (21). Similarly, columns (23 and 24) replace the salience based measure in column (22) by *media concern* measure constructed using Eq. (7) on news related to both migrants and Muslims, with tone measured by our custom dictionary in column (23) and by ChatPGT in column (24). Lastly, columns (26 and 27) replace the salience based measure in column (25) by *media concern* measure constructed using Eq. (7) on news discussing both migrants and security related issues, with tone measured by our custom dictionary in column (26) and by ChatPGT in column (27). Standard errors are clustered at the department level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

Table 8: Impact of NATIONAL media Concern about migration (Tone-weighted Salience Measure, Small Cities (Less Than 2,000 Inhabitants))

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>								
	Δ_Vote								
	(28)	(29)	(30)	(31)	(32)	(33)	(34)	(35)	(36)
$\Delta_Salience_Immigration_News_Nat$	-4.28 (7.77)								
$\Delta_Salience_Immigration_Tone_Weighted_Nat$		-1.10 (8.45)							
$\Delta_Salience_Immigration_Tone_Weighted_GPT_Nat$			-3.29 (8.00)						
$\Delta_Salience_Muslims_News_Nat$				3.81* (2.16)					
$\Delta_Salience_Muslims_Tone_Weighted_Nat$					3.73* (2.11)				
$\Delta_Salience_Muslims_Tone_Weighted_GPT_Nat$						3.76* (2.13)			
$\Delta_Salience_Security_News_Nat$							2.80* (1.67)		
$\Delta_Salience_Security_Tone_Weighted_Nat$								2.74* (1.63)	
$\Delta_Salience_Security_Tone_Weighted_GPT_Nat$									2.78* (1.65)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	18.55*** (2.65)	18.61*** (2.69)	18.59*** (2.66)	17.35*** (2.77)	17.34*** (2.77)	17.35*** (2.77)	17.67*** (2.71)	17.65*** (2.71)	17.66*** (2.71)
Observations	28,082	28,082	28,082	28,082	28,082	28,082	28,082	28,082	28,082
R ²	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18
Adjusted R ²	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18

Notes: This table presents the estimates from regressing the change in voting for the far-right party from 2010 to 2015 on the change in National media exposure, for very small cities with less than 2,000 inhabitants, using the specification in Eq (6). In columns (28, 31 and 34) we examine how votes for the far-right party respond to National media reporting on immigration issues, using a salience-based measure of Immigration news, and a salience-based measure of news related to both migrants and Muslims, as well as news discussing both immigrants and security related issues respectively. In columns (29 and 30), we replace the salience based measure in column (28) by *media concern* measure constructed using Eq. (7), with tone measured by our custom dictionary in column (29) and by ChatPGT in column (30). Similarly, columns (32 and 33) replace the salience based measure in column (31) by *media concern* measure constructed using Eq. (7) on news related to both migrants and Muslims, with tone measured by our custom dictionary in column (32) and by ChatPGT in column (33). Lastly, columns (35 and 36) replace the salience based measure in column (34) by *media concern* measure constructed using Eq. (7) on news discussing both migrants and security related issues, with tone measured by our custom dictionary in column (35) and by ChatPGT in column (36). Standard errors are clustered at the department level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

4.7 Coefficient Stability Test

Although the causal effect of media exposure estimated above appears robust, concerns about omitted variable bias remain. Specifically, unobserved changes in voters’ preferences after the attack could confound the relationship between media exposure and election results. To address this, we have begun by considering exposure to National newspapers only as a sort of instrument to global exposure to news.

Despite this control, some might still argue that unobservable shifts in voter preferences or other factors could still bias the estimates. To rigorously assess the extent of this potential bias, we apply the methodology proposed by [Oster \(2019\)](#), which evaluates the stability of our coefficient of interest had we had access to more observables. In practice, this approach compares estimated coefficients and R^2 values from models with varying levels of controls.

At the bottom of [Table 9](#), we report two key metrics derived from this method, δ^* — the proportional bias due to unobservables required to reduce the treatment effect (media exposure δ) to zero and β^* — the lower bound of the treatment effect under equal selection on observables and unobservables. Following [Oster \(2019\)](#), we assume a maximal R^2 that is 30% larger than the R^2 from the controlled regression—a conservative assumption given the context of our study.

For news specifically about immigrants and Muslims (columns 1–3 in [table 7](#)), the δ value is 2.23, indicating that selection on unobservables would need to be more than twice as strong as selection on observables to nullify the treatment effect. The corresponding lower-bound β estimates range from 2.49 to 2.56. For news linking immigration with security concerns (columns 4–6), the δ values range from 2.51 to 2.53, suggesting even stronger robustness. The β estimates for this category range from 2.03 to 2.08. These findings strongly suggest that unobservables are unlikely to explain away the observed positive coefficients for media exposure variables. In practical terms, the results support the causal interpretation that increased exposure to news linking immigration with Muslims or security concerns following the attack significantly contributed to the rise in far-right voting.

Table 9: Coefficient Stability

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>					
	Δ_Vote					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
$\Delta_Salience_Muslims_News_Nat$	4.29** (2.16)					
$\Delta_Salience_Muslims_Tone_Weighted_Nat$		4.19** (2.11)				
$\Delta_Salience_Muslims_Tone_Weighted_GPT_Nat$			4.24** (2.13)			
$\Delta_Salience_Security_News_Nat$				3.26* (1.69)		
$\Delta_Salience_Security_Tone_Weighted_Nat$					3.18* (1.64)	
$\Delta_Salience_Security_Tone_Weighted_GPT_Nat$						3.23* (1.67)
Controls Used	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
δ^* for $\beta = 0$	2.23	2.23	2.23	2.53	2.51	2.52
β^* for $\delta = 1$	2.56	2.49	2.52	2.08	2.03	2.07
Constant	19.32*** (2.34)	19.32*** (2.34)	19.32*** (2.34)	19.66*** (2.26)	19.64*** (2.26)	19.65*** (2.26)
Observations	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678	32,678
R ²	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17
Adjusted R ²	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17

Notes: This table presents the results of the sensitivity analysis of our findings to omitted variable bias. In columns (1 to 3), we examine how votes for the far-right party respond to National media reporting on immigration and Muslims, using a salience-based measure in column (1), and *media concern* measure constructed using Eq. (7), with tone measured by our custom dictionary in column (2) and by ChatPGT in column (3). In columns (3 to 6), we examine how votes for the far-right party respond to National media reporting on immigration and security issues using a salience-based measure in column (4), and *media concern* measure constructed using Eq. (7), with tone measured by our custom dictionary in column (5) and by ChatPGT in column (6). For each specification, we report δ^* , estimates which represent, the degree of selection on unobservables relative to observables (with respect to the treatment variable) that would be necessary to eliminate the result as well as β^* estimates, which represent the bias-adjusted treatment effect. Standard errors are clustered at the department level. Statistical significance levels are indicated as * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$.

4.8 Media Contribution to the Rise of the Extreme Right after November 13

Using the results from Table 7 (columns 23) and the observed changes in media exposure across all *Départements* in France, we can now estimate the contribution of media concern about immigration and Muslims to the rise in votes for the main anti-immigration party in each locality. The median contribution to the vote share for the anti-migrant party across all localities is approximately 1.82%. However, there is significant heterogeneity across all of our *Départements*. The lowest contribution is around 0.42%, while the highest contribution, observed in the *Départements* of Ardèche, is around 12.89%. Figure 13 summarizes the results across all *Départements* in France.²⁶ As shown, in the majority of localities the contribution to the vote share does not exceed 5%, although in the southeast, many *Départements* see contributions exceeding 10%.

In summary, while the overall contribution of media exposure may not be substantial in most *Départements*, the effect is notably significant in certain regions. Although the National Front did not eventually win the regional elections in any *Département* and a fortiori any French region, it is plausible that the party that did win—primarily the right-wing *Les Républicains* in the southeast—may have responded to this surge in support for the far-right by adopting tougher regional policies on immigration.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we utilized natural language processing techniques to analyze news articles on immigration published before and after three major terrorist events in 2015 and 2016 in France. We specifically examined whether these events caused shifts in both the intensity of reporting and the content of news about immigrants, as well as the duration of these changes. Furthermore, we assessed the impact of the media’s portrayal of migrants following the November 13, 2015, terrorist attack on the voting outcomes for the main anti-immigration party in France. Our approach offers a comprehensive test of whether news media content can be held partly responsible for the recent surge in the popularity of the extreme right in

²⁶As noted earlier, we exclude the results related to the Île-de-France region.

France.

Our findings strongly support the argument that terrorism significantly affects media attitudes toward immigrants. Following the 2015 and 2016 terrorist attacks, the salience of immigration in media coverage increased sharply, especially when linked to terms such as “Muslims” or “(in)security”. This increased media focus, coupled with a deteriorating tone—more pronounced in left-leaning newspapers—was intense but short-lived. Our analysis reveals that municipalities exposed to more negative media coverage experienced a relatively small rise in votes for anti-migrant parties in the closest elections to one of the terror events being studied. However, the average effect hides a large heterogeneity across french localities (in one of them it has been measured to be contributing around 12.59% of the vote share increase).

The findings of this study have significant implications for media regulation, public policy, and political strategy. Media portrayals of migrants, particularly after terrorist events, can unintentionally amplify divisive narratives, fostering negative public attitudes and bolstering support for anti-migrant policies. Policymakers should consider implementing media regulations that encourage balanced and responsible reporting, especially in times of crisis, to prevent the unintentional reinforcement of harmful stereotypes and societal divisions.

This paper is relevant to the ongoing debate on the effectiveness of terrorist attacks in achieving political objectives. It extends existing knowledge on the relationship between terrorism and electoral outcomes by highlighting the media’s influential role in shaping voter preferences in the aftermath of such events. While our findings align with previous research on the effects of terrorist attacks on election outcomes, they expand the literature by quantifying the electoral impact of media salience and tone, providing robust empirical evidence that enriches theoretical discussions on media influence during crises.

However, this study faces limitations. The focus on France limits the generalizability of our findings to other contexts with different media landscapes and political environments, and the study’s temporal scope may not capture the long-term dynamics of media influence on voting behavior.

Future research should consider cross-country comparisons to assess whether the observed effects are consistent across various media and political contexts. Exploring the role of social

media alongside traditional media could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how different platforms shape public opinion and influence voting behavior. Additionally, investigating the long-term effects of media coverage on political attitudes could reveal whether short-term changes in sentiment lead to enduring shifts in public policy and societal attitudes towards migrants.

Given the crucial role of media in shaping public discourse, particularly during crises, this study calls for a reevaluation of media practices, especially in reporting on sensitive issues like migration in the wake of terrorism. Balanced and responsible journalism is essential for maintaining social harmony and protecting democratic values, ensuring that media serve to inform rather than inflame public sentiment during challenging times.

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Appendix A Impact per Attack

Figure 14: Charlie Hebdo - Saliency Point Estimate with 90% CI

Figure 15: Charlie Hebdo - Tone Point Estimate with 90% CI

Figure 16: The Bataclan - Saliency Point Estimate with 90% CI

Figure 17: The Bataclan - Tone Point Estimate with 90% CI

Figure 18: Nice - Salience Point Estimate with 90% CI

Figure 19: Nice - Tone Point Estimate with 90% CI

Appendix B Descriptive statistics

Table 10 displays the distribution of the identified sub-components across the media for media with at least 20 news articles about immigration within the time frame of the study. The column “Presse” shows the name of the news media, the column “All news” displays the count of all news articles of the specified media that exist within the archive Europress and Factiva, the column “Immigration news” displays the count news articles identified as being linked to immigration, the column “% Immigration” displays the percentage of all news articles that is

related to immigration, the remaining columns display the percentage of the category mentioned within immigration news. It is important to acknowledge that the sum of percentages across categories may surpass 100% that is because an article can be assigned to more than one category.

Table 10: List of the newspapers, characteristics and descriptive statistics.

Presse	Regional/national and P Orientation	All news	Immigration news	% Immigration	% Immigration + Muslims	% Immigration + Humanitarian	% Immigration + Economy	% Immigration + (In)security
1	Acteurs publics	8324	86	1.03	4.65	27.91	38.37	25.58
2	Aujourd'hui en France	1322736	1069	0.08	15.25	30.87	11.79	33.12
3	Le Berry Républicain	279544	272	0.10	5.15	18.38	15.44	7.35
4	Centre Presse Aveyron	432738	510	0.12	16.08	34.51	9.61	30.59
5	Charente Libre	493225	536	0.11	14.55	37.87	11.19	24.81
6	Le Courrier de l'Ouest	3516243	1481	0.04	9.18	25.25	9.32	14.58
7	La Croix	870938	1705	0.20	16.36	37.71	20.18	24.40
8	L'Express	65805	394	0.60	28.68	21.57	50.76	41.62
9	Le Figaro	9868208	2943	0.03	28.03	34.59	25.38	41.28
10	Le Havre Libre	1789	25	1.40	0.00	20.00	8.00	20.00
11	L'Humanité	496458	1346	0.27	20.58	39.45	27.64	38.11
12	Le Journal du Centre	338702	362	0.11	2.76	21.27	8.56	11.60
13	L'Est Républicain	1277075	2195	0.02	10.52	32.98	12.94	21.87
14	L'Indépendant	2843052	1033	0.04	14.81	33.59	11.42	28.36
15	La Nouvelle République Dimanche	84874	184	0.22	9.24	27.17	9.24	23.91
16	La Nouvelle République du Centre-Ouest	8607653	1609	0.02	9.51	28.71	11.31	16.59
17	La République des Pyrénées	834301	1732	0.21	22.40	48.21	14.38	41.11
18	La Voix du Nord	14495683	4232	0.03	3.95	18.38	7.30	21.41
19	La Provence	8589400	2312	0.03	9.99	23.31	11.42	18.21
20	Le Bien Public	1250382	614	0.05	8.14	31.60	13.52	19.38
21	Le Journal de Saône et Loire	2402216	731	0.03	8.89	36.39	13.95	19.29
22	Le main libre	225817	223	0.10	5.83	22.42	7.62	6.73
23	Libération	681378	1785	0.26	27.45	34.34	28.07	38.71
24	Midi Libre	10112085	1698	0.02	16.90	30.92	12.96	28.50
25	Le Monde	5395026	3272	0.06	28.27	36.31	32.61	41.29
26	Ouest-France	114427294	4557	0.00	7.15	35.90	10.82	14.31
27	Paris-Normandie	832455	543	0.07	11.42	33.15	14.92	29.47
28	Le Parisien	4148000	1840	0.04	10.16	36.58	8.37	19.35
29	Le Point	213506	424	0.20	40.80	26.65	49.29	53.77
30	Presse-Océan	987714	735	0.07	14.56	31.02	8.03	23.95
31	Le Progrès	18661920	2025	0.01	9.19	43.36	27.51	22.67
32	Sud Ouest	27838020	3430	0.01	11.98	37.29	15.60	28.34
33	Le Télégramme	9343835	1413	0.02	7.71	34.18	9.91	13.16
34	Valeurs Actuelles	63823	776	1.22	49.61	22.16	36.60	55.28

B.1 Salience: Mean before, after and for the study period

Sub.Components	Mean Before Terror	Mean During Terror	Mean for the study period
1 Immigration	0.30% (SD = 0.07)	0.57% (SD = 0.24)	0.53% (SD = 0.24)
2 Immigration + Muslims	0.02% (SD = 0.02)	0.04% (SD = 0.02)	0.03% (SD = 0.02)
3 Immigration + Security	0.07% (SD = 0.03)	0.14% (SD = 0.06)	0.13% (SD = 0.06)
4 Immigration + Economy	0.06% (SD = 0.02)	0.07% (SD = 0.03)	0.08% (SD = 0.03)
5 Immigration + Humanitarian	0.02% (SD = 0.01)	0.11% (SD = 0.12)	0.09% (SD = 0.11)

B.2 Tone: Mean before, after and for the study period

Sub.Components	Mean Before Terror	Mean During Terror	Mean for the study period
1 Immigration	0.0164 (SD = 0.008)	0.0161 (SD = 0.005)	0.0162 (SD =0.006)
2 Immigration + Muslims	0.0012 (SD = 0.008)	(-) 0.0018 (SD = 0.008)	(-) 0.0013 (SD = 0.008)
3 Immigration + Security	0.0004 (SD = 0.008)	(-) 0.0037 (SD = 0.006)	(-) 0.0031 (SD = 0.006)
4 Immigration + Economy	0.0226 (SD = 0.005)	0.0225 (SD = 0.005)	0.0225 (SD = 0.005)
5 Immigration + Humanitarian	0.0415 (SD = 0.009)	0.0393 (SD = 0.010)	0.0396 (SD =0.010)

B.3 Mean before and During Terror by Media Group

Group	Period	Salience	Tone	Salience	Tone
		Immigration	Immigration	Muslims	Muslims
Right	Before Terror	2.35	0.009	0.85	-0.0047
	During Terror	3.97	0.006	1.38	-0.0016
Center	Before Terror	1.65	0.008	0.23	-0.0006
	During Terror	2.32	0.007	0.37	-0.0003
Left	Before Terror	2.49	0.013	0.41	-0.0003
	During Terror	4.51	0.011	0.64	0.00226
Regional	Before Terror	0.42	0.019	0.07	-0.00622
	During Terror	0.80	0.019	0.10	-0.007

Table 11: Salience and Tone of Immigration and Immigration + Muslims Before and During Terror Events.

1. The column mean before terror displays the mean for the specified category before beginning of the phases of terrorism (from the 1st October 2014 to the 6th of January 2015, inclusive).
2. The column mean after terror displays the mean for the specified category from the date of the first terrorist attack (Charlie Hebdo) until the last date of our study period, from the 7th of January 2015 until the 31st of October 2016.
3. the column mean for the study period displays the mean of the specified category for all dates present in the dataset, from the 1st of October 2014 to the 31st of October 2016.

(a) Share of News References to Immigration (Mean Salience)

(b) Mean Tone Score of News References to Immigration

(c) Share of News References to Immigration + Muslims (Mean Salience)

(d) Mean Tone Score of News References to Immigration + Muslims

Figure 20: Mean Salience and Tone of Immigration and Immigration + Muslims News

B.4 Immigration + Economy

Figure 21: Weekly count of news that link Immigration to Economic issues

B.5 Immigration + Humanitarian

Figure 22: Weekly count of news that discusses the humanitarian side of immigration

B.6 Dictionary Validation

B.7 Top medias across categories

B.8 Impact by Media Groups

We now turn to examining the impact of the attacks across different media groups based on political orientation, following the classification provided by Science Po (see previous section).

We concentrate on right-leaning and Left-leaning media in what follows. ²⁷

²⁷ *Le Monde* is the only journal that is classified at the center (center left) and the number of articles evoking migration is relatively small (around 100 observations), which is why we do not show here the results for the center media.

Figure 23: Author's Dictionary Validation by ChatGPT

Figure 24: ChatGPT's Dictionary validation by the Authors

Figure 25: ChatGPT's Dictionary validation by Itself

Figure 26: LSDFr Dictionary Validation by the Authors

Figure 27: LSDFr Dictionary Validation by ChatGPT

Figure 28: Top medias across categories

B.8.1 Right-Leaning Media

The right-leaning media in our dataset include: *Valeurs Actuelles*, *Le Figaro*, *Le Point* and *L'Express*, collectively providing approximately 416 observations on migrants related articles overtime, which we analyze here.

As discussed in Section 2, right-leaning media consistently exhibited a more negative tone towards migrants throughout the entire period of study (both before and during the terror events), alongside relatively high salience, particularly in comparison to centrist outlets. Specifically, 2.3% of the articles from right-oriented media mentioned migrants before the attacks (i.e., before 2015), and of those, about one-third (around 0.8%) also mentioned Muslims. In contrast, only 0.07% of articles in other journals mentioned both Muslims and migrants—more than 10 times lower than the right-leaning media’s figure.²⁸

Figures 29 and 30 illustrate how right-wing media responded to the terrorist attacks. While the estimates are less precise due to the reduced sample size, we observe that the behavior of right-leaning media aligns with the general media trends in terms of the direction and persistence of effects. However, in terms of magnitude, the effects differ significantly.

Starting with Figure 29, in a purely statistical sense, the share of news linking immigration to Muslims increased significantly for at least four weeks. However, for weeks 5 and 6, the point estimates for the Muslim-specific sub-sample are positive and almost statistically significant at the 10% level (the zero coefficient lies within the confidence interval, but the interval suggests that the true estimate is likely positive). The estimates are similar for the insecurity-specific sub-sample, though with wider confidence intervals, making the coefficients statistically insignificant from Week 3 onward. In terms of magnitude, during the three weeks following Week 0, the average effect on salience can be estimated at roughly 1.5 percentage points. This increase raises the salience of articles citing both migrants and Muslims to 2.3%, compared to 0.85% just before the attacks. This represents more than a 2.7-fold increase in the wake of the events, compared to the pre-attack period.

Turning to the tone regression, summarized in Figure 30, we find that the tone related to the two sub-samples (Muslims and insecurity-related issues) deteriorated for approximately two weeks (Weeks 0 and 1). A more liberal interpretation of the results could extend this

²⁸Around 78% of the journals are regional, and 80% of the observations come from regional publications.

negative impact on tone to Weeks 2 and 3, though for Week 3, we cannot reject the hypothesis that the true coefficient value is zero at a strict 10% significance level. In terms of magnitude, the net tone measure was, on average, around -0.005 before 2015. The average point estimate for the Muslim-specific sub-sample during the three weeks following the attacks is approximately -0.008, lowering the tone measure to -0.013—more than 2.5 times lower than its pre-2015 level.

Figure 29: Right leaning media - Saliency Point Estimate with 90% CI

Figure 30: Right leaning media - Tone Point Estimate with 90% CI

B.8.2 Left-Leaning Media

The left-leaning media outlets in our dataset include: La Croix, Liberation and L’Humanité, which collectively provide approximately 312 observations used in the following analysis.

Figure 31 and 32 present the outcomes. In terms of salience, these media seem to react in a more persistent manner compared to the general trends observed for right-leaning outlets (as discussed in Section 2). Specifically, regarding the salience of Muslims in migration-related coverage, the positive impact, though declining over time, remains quasi-statistically significant even after the seventh week following the terror attacks.

In terms of magnitude, the impact on salience for left-leaning journals is relatively modest. From an initial share of 0.4% of articles discussing Muslims, the salience increases to 0.9% during the first three weeks, representing a 2.25-fold increase. Interestingly, after Week 2, the salience decreases, stabilizing at a new, higher plateau of around 0.65% by Week 6 and 7, with an incremental effect of approximately 0.25 percentage points. However, this parameter is only marginally statistically significant, hovering slightly above the 10% threshold.

Turning to Figure 32, we observe a significant change in tone in Week 0 for left-leaning journals when discussing Muslims. Starting from a nearly neutral tone of around -0.0003, there is a sharp negative shift of more than 30 times, with the tone decreasing by -0.01 in Week 0. This negative effect on Muslim-related articles diminishes after one week. Interestingly, the negative tone persists for two weeks in articles discussing immigration more broadly, with a magnitude similar to that observed in the Muslim-specific sub-sample. The effect almost carries over into Week 2, though it becomes statistically insignificant at the 10% level.

To summarize, left-leaning media do cite Muslim migrants more frequently after the attacks. Besides, the tone shifts dramatically to a more negative stance, much more so than the tone shifts observed in right-leaning media. This may be due to the fact that, prior to the attacks, left-leaning media generally exhibited a positive tone towards migrants overall (and a neutral tone towards Muslim migrants specifically), which became sharply negative in the aftermath of the attacks.

Figure 31: Left leaning Media - Saliency Point Estimate with 90% CI

Figure 32: Left leaning Media - Tone Point Estimate with 90% CI

B.8.3 The Regional Press

Lastly, we examine the reaction of the regional press, as shown in Figure 33 and 34, based on approximately 3,200 observations.²⁹

²⁹List of the regional press in our data together with the number of immigration news published by each media between parentheses: Ouest-France (4557), La Voix du Nord (4232), Sud-Ouest (3430), La Provence (2312), L'Est Républicain (2195), Le Parisien (1840), La République des Pyrénées (1732), Midi Libre (1698), La Nouvelle République du Centre-Ouest (1609), Aujourd'hui en France (1069), Le Courrier de l'Ouest (1481), Le Télégramme (1413), L'Indépendant (1033), Presse-Océan (735), Le Journal de Saône et Loire (731), Le

The share of news linking immigration to Muslims or security concerns increased for about two weeks following the terrorist attacks. This represents a significant rise in salience, increasing from 0.07% before the attacks to 0.15% during the first three weeks. However, this increase is smaller compared to that observed in national journals.

Regarding tone, the sentiment in articles linking immigration to insecurity and Muslims deteriorated during the week of the attack. The absolute value of the tone measure increased by approximately 2.65 times, from -0.006 before 2015 to -0.016 immediately after the attacks. This magnitude is comparable to the effect observed in right-leaning journals, though it is much smaller than the sharp tone deterioration observed in left-leaning outlets.

To conclude, the left-leaning press seems to react more than the rest of the media after the terror shocks.

Figure 33: The regional press - Salience Point Estimate with 90% CI

Bien Public (614), Paris-Normandie (543), Charente Libre (536), Centre Presse Aveyron (510), Le Journal du Centre (362), Le Berry Républicain (272), Le main libre (223), La Nouvelle République Dimanche (184), Acteurs publics (86), Le Havre Libre (25).

Figure 34: The regional press - Tone Point Estimate with 90% CI

Appendix C The dictionary

C.1 positive words

“*aboutir, abri, acceptable, acception, accepter, accessibilité, acclame, accompagnement, accomplie, accord, accorder, accueil, accueille, accueillir, accès, accélérer, acquitter, action, adaptation, adapter, adaptée, admirer, adoration, adoucir, aide, aider, aimer, aimon, aisance, aiser, ajustement, aliment, alimentaire, allier, allié, allocation, allocation familial, allouer, alternatif, amadouer, ambiance, ambitieux, ambition, ambitionn, ami, amical, amitier, amour, amoureux, amélioration, améliorer, aménagement, ange, angélique, apaisante, aplanir, applaudi, applaudissement, apport, apprendre, apprentissage, approbation, approuver, asile, assainissement, assidûment, association, assouplir, assouplissement, assurance, assurer, atout, attractivité, authentique, avantage, beau, bel, belle, bien, bienveillance, bienvenu, bise, blague, boisson, bon, bonheur, boulot, bravo, brille, briller, business, bénéficié, bénéficiaire, bénévolat, bénévole, café, calme, calmer, camarade, capable, carrière, certitude, champagne, chance, chanter, chantier, ciner, citoyenneter, civilisation, clément, cohabitation, cohérent, cohésion, cohésion social, collaboration, collect, collecte, collecter, collectif, commerce, commercial, communauté, communauté vie, communion, compassion, comprend, compréhensible, compétence, compétitivité, concret, concrétisent, confectionner, confiance, confiant, conforme, confort, confrère, conscience, conseil, conseiller, consommation, consommer, constructif, construit, consulter, contribuer, contribution, convaincre, convergence, converger, conviction, convivial, convié, coopération, coordinateur, coordination, coriace, cotisation, cotiser, coté, courageux, couverture, croire, croissance, créateur, créatif, création, créativité, crédible, créer, culte, culture, culturel, culturelle, célèbre, célébrer, dansante, danse, dialogue, dignité, diplomatique, disponible, distribuer, distribution, diversifier, don, donner, donneur, douceur, droit, durable, dynamisme, débat, déboucher, décevant, décision, décisionnelle, décor, décoration, découverte, défendre, défense, défilé, déjeuner, déjouer, désamorcer, désir, détendue, développé, dîne, efficace, efficacité, efficience, effort, embauche, embaucher, embrasse, emmaü, empathie, emploi, emploie, employer, encadrement, encourageant, encourager, engagement, engagé, entente, enthousiaste, entraid, entreprendre, entrepreneur, espérance, espérer, espéron, essentielle, exceptionnel, excuser, exonérer, fabriquer, facile, facilement, faciliter, familial, famille, fasciner, faveur, favorable, favori, favoriser, festif, festival, fiable, fidèle, fidélité, fier, financement, financer, financier, financée, fleurissement, flexibilité, fondation, force, formation, formidable, fort, fortune, france terre immigration, franchement, fraternel, fraternelle, fraternité, fulgurant, fête, gagner, gentiment, grand littérature française, gratuit, gratuitement, guide, généreux, générosité, gérer, gîte, habile, harmonie, heureux, hommage, honneur, honnêteter, honorer, hospitalité, humain, humaine, humainement, humanisme, humaniste, humanitaire, humanité, humour, huppé, héberge, hébergement, héberger, héritage, héros, idéal, imaginer, impressionner, inciter, inclusif, incontestable, incontesté, indemniser, industrialisation, informer, infrastructure, innocenté, innovation, innover, insertion, inspiration, inspirer, installation, installer, installée, insérer, intellectuel, intelligence, intelligent, intime, intégration, intégrer, intégrité, intégré, intéressant, intéresse, intérêt, inventer, investir, investissement, investissent, invité, jeu, jeune, joie, joli, jouer, jouet, jouon, joyeux, laissez-passer, laurier, laïcité, libert, liberté, libre, libéralisation, libéraliser, libère, libérer, liquidité, loger, logique,*

loisir, lucide, lucidité, lucratif, lumineuse, lumière, légal, légalement, légerter, légitimité, maîtriser, malin, martyr, maîtriser, meilleur, merci, mieux, miséricorde, mixité, mobiliser, mobilité, moderne, modèle, modérer, moins difficile, monument, motiver, multiculturalisme, muscler, médicament, mélange, mérite, métier, nourrir, nourriture, nouveau, nouveauté, Noël, nutrition, négociation, obtenir, oeuvre, offert, offerte, offre, offrir, offron, ong, opportunité, optimisme, organisation, organiser, orientation, ouvert, ouverte, ouverture, ouvrir, ovationner, pacifier, paix, parcours, pardon, pardonner, parfaire, parrainage, partager, partenair, partenariat, participation, participer, participeron, passionner, patriote, penser, perfectionnement, plaider, plaisanterie, plaisir, pluralité, poliment, popularité, positif, possibilité, possible, poème, prier, primer, prioritaire, privilégier, prière, productiviste, professionnalisation, professionnaliser, professionnel, profit, profite, profiter, progresse, projet, promenade, promotion, promouvoir, proposé, propre, prospère, prospérité, protecteur, protection, protéger, prouesse, précaution, précieuse, préparation, présent, préservation, préserver, prévention, puissance, pédagogie, pérenne, qualifié, raisonnable, raisonnablement, rapprocher, rassembler, rassurant, rassure, ratifier, ravi, raviver, recrutement, recruter, recréer, redonner, refonder, refuge, relancer, relaxer, relie, reloger, remercier, remobilisation, renaissance, renforcer, renfort, renommé, renouer, renouveler, repas, respecter, respectueux, responsable, ressource, restaurer, rever, riche, richesses, rigueur, rire, réception, réchauffer, récompenser, réconciliation, réconcilier, réconfort, régal, réglée, régulariser, réhabilitation, réinsertion, réinsérer, réintégration, réintégrer, réjouissante, rémunérer, rénovation, rénover, réorientation, réouverture, république, résilience, résolution, résoudre, résurrection, rétablissemer, rétribution, réussir, rêve, sagement, salaire, saluer, sang froid, santé, satisfaction, sauver, sauveront, sauvetage, sauveteur, scolarisation, scolariser, secourir, secours, sensibilisation, sensibiliser, sensible, service, servir, sincère, social, socle, soin, solidaire, solidarité, sollicitude, solution, solvabilité, soucier, souhaiter, soulagée, soupe, sourire, soutenir, soutien, sportif, spécialiste, stabilisation, stabilité, stable, stratégique, structurée, subvention, succès, suffire, supporter, supérieur, surmonter, survie, survivant, survivre, sympathique, sécurisation, sécuriser, sécurité, sérieux, sérénité, talent, tendresse, terre mélange, tolérance, transparence, travail, travaille, travailler, travailleur, trophée, unanime, union, unité, universalisme, universelle, utile, utopie, valeur, validité, vertueux, victoir, victoire, victorieux, vie, visible, vision, vivre, vivre - ensembl, volontaire, volontier, volonté, vouloir, vrai, vraie, véritable, vérité, vêtement, échange, échanger, échapper, échapper enfermement, éclairer, éclairé, écolo, écologie, écologique, économique, édification, éducateur, éducation, égalité, élite, émanciper, émergent, émotion, émoi, énergie, énergétique, équilibre, équitable, étincillant, évolution

C.2 Negative words

“oligarchie, catastrophe, pièger, surabondance, pesant, bloquer, contaminer, anxiété, tyrannie, confisquer, tension, interdire, tenté, menacer, intimidation, regrette, pardon, endoctriner, truand, pann, brutalité, narcissique, dissimulé, expulser, crise identitaire, tué, provoquer, renseignement, détresse, obligation, débarquer, méchanceté, obstacle, abattre, fixer réfugié, arme, peur, discréditer, impuissance, hospitalier, engorger, impréparation, plaindre, exiguë, détruire, dévaster, empêcher, recours, illégal, sexisme, incident, rechercher, judiciaire, poison, envahi, barrer, hurlement, écrouler, déploré, prétendre, atrociter, interdiction, renvoyer, djihadiste, sabotage, être -

dire, criminalité, déloyal, pénitentiaire, empêche, exagéron, fauteur, suppression, attentat, tragédie, contagion, fanatique, démantèlement, destruction, dominer, insuffisante, encombrer, critique, zone gris, escalade, accuser, chantage, squatter, inhumain, criminaliser, peiner, bavure, djihad, islamophob, encellulement, soldat, contre, dommage, sombrer, réduit, accusation, daech, déficit, sécurité, incompetent, craquent, "anti-étranger", priver, voler, isoler, exécuter, gesticulation, déclin, massive, bête, lacunaire, risque, criminel, fatigue, dégénérer, cantonné, noie, naufrage, médical, sale, fermeture, submerger, embarcation, battre, déshumanisation, démission, insulter, arsenal, rétention, fragmentation, incertitude, hystérie, faiblesse, accablement, loin consensuel, bombe, désinvolve, mourir, tribunal, fumeux, ignoble, laxisme, violence, émotion, piéger, éliminé, ras-le-bol, détourné, inadapté, abandonnée, accuse, réactionnaire, djihadist, ne passer pas, nuancer, effroyable, souffrir, saturation, sinistrose, identitaire, chaotique, violation, hypothermie, fusil-mitrailleur, islamisme, taper, enfermé, déborder, pointer, djihadisme, exploiter, gendarmerie, choquer, contrevérité, parquet, faiblard, découper, grossièrement, illusion, tirer, renier, défaut, malade, démanteler, meurtrier, armer, virulent, frisson, perdre, instrumentaliser, omerta, bagarre, invasion, allergie, pique, injurieux, désaccord, fusil, clivage, réaction, perdraient, illettrisme, assourdissant, immonde, artificiellement, excès, érosion, mort, assaut, disparition, évacuer, anti-migrant, violent, serré, xénophobie, monstrueux, exorbiter, couteau, malheureux, déplorer, horrible, licenciement, resurgir, bactérie, tsunami, risquent, éloignement, ignorer, bombarder, éclaté, difficulté, addiction, machisme, néocolonial, dégradante, terreur, ébranler, explosion, cagoulé, opposer, enfer, mauvais, inadaptation, gangrener, braquage, fragmenter, ivre, diabète, squat, crainte, débouter, criminologie, chavirer, dette, foire empoigne, turbulence, incompatible, colère, fou, soi-diser, "anti-immigré", interminable, vulnérabilité, défaillant, division, gaspillage, génocid, banditisme, martial, laxiste, condamnaient, ciblé, réticence, faim, danger, déclasser, hospitalisation, hostile, abuser, explosif, esclavage, inconnu, charge, criminel, outrage, projectile, populiste, furieux, rechigner, interpeller, insensible, combat, écriquer, illégalement, égoïsme, éliminer, caniveau, raciste, fâcher, dérobé, évacuation, intransigent, précarité, fragile, espionnage, confrontation, dégrader, condamné, incertain, vertige, pollution, escroquerie, incapacité, amende, tair, protester, critiquer, polémique, amalgame, abattre, détenu, guerre, illettré, battu, intrigué, jihad, assassinat, gâcher, souffre, embarcation fortunée, bataille, désolation, effondrement, entasser, répugnant, endeuiller, tourmente, enfourcher, cassé, décès, hurler, strict, dénoncer, paranoïa, inégalité, trouble, contradiction, interdire, jamais, gâchée, risquer, décadence, regretter, absurde, impopularité, incontrôlable, insulte, contester, sinistre, gravement, traître, maudire, empirer, communautarisme, contrôle, guérilla, sécuritaire, déscolariser, plonger, piège, désespérer, autoritarisme, malédiction, mortem, trafiquant, inutile, échapper, ment, scepticisme, eurosceptique, foutre, soumission, incohérent, ombre, difficile, insalubrité, impuissance, gaspiller, déchet, offenser, cellule, dispersion, fatal, hôpital, "dae", fièvre, contrainte, ingérable, puni, accusent, tuer, crouler, épuisement, contraint, grever, autarcie, insensibiliser, démunir, cogner, traîner, incomplet, malhonnêteté, contentieux, inquiet, diviser, qaïda, fichage, fâche, pessimisme, jihadiste, juge, disparaître, paresseux, torrentiel, inquisiteur, tomber, dangérosité, prisonnier, fracture, casseur, ravager, nationaliste, combattant, ghettoïsation, dénonciation, débordement, farce, violeur, dictature, pression, dénigrer, purger, impopulaire, dangereux, déracinement, sauter, assassin, déçoit, retirer, étouffer, handicap, cracher, échec, destructeur, couper, impasse, affaiblir, ch, étrangler, exploité, détonateur,

loin, instabilité, retard, rivalité, châtie, malheur, affaiblissement, indifférer, scarifiée, incarcérer, spolie, clandestin, injustice, interpellation, stigmatiser, dégat, maladie, perte, instable, pourrir, médiéval, terrifier, condamnation, détérioration, enfoncer, perquisition, masochisme, problème, outrance, négatif, désintégration, adultère, réticent, piégé, poussiéreux, traumatique, désastre, piller, perturber, faille, lacrymogène, abandonner, négatif, indignation, redouter, tort, prison, grincer, confronter, affaiblie, effrayer, déloger, dégradé, arrêté, exclusion, détention, lutter, renoncer, dépit, discrédité, déchaîner, espion, meurtre, provocation, faute, mitrailler, tueur, menace, forteresse europe, rejeter, funeste, épouvanté, blessé, complice, suspicion, tromper, vainement, cadavre, anti-loi, défaite, barbelé, impossible, déstabiliser, clôture, surpeupler, vulnérable, hooliganisme, erreur, corrompue, préjugé, besoin, mafia, frileux, paralyser, déconfite, rebelle, violer, indigne, solitaire, idéologie, ironie, craint, pilleur, drogue, drame, rixe, inexistant, déception, harcèlement, fermenter, aggraver, sceptique, dépression, crever, prostitution, méprise, choc, durcir, gendarme, extrémisme, coup, précipitation, vague, limite, traumatiser, insécurité, dégringoler, chaos, reconduit, secouer, sentence, abus, expulsé, overdose, colon, pénible, pnr, coupable, charlatan, soupçon, seuil tolérance, infamie, inférieur, péril, persécution, indifférence, attroupelement, misère, tendre, excessif, dérapage, provocateur, perdu, disperser, raté, excrément, antiterroriste, vague réfugié, frapper, complication, compliquer, radical, noyade, sans-papiers, trahison, agresser, terrorisée, cavale, accrochage, discrimination, venger, rien, urgence, sanctionner, sombre, ruine, trahi, écrase, refuser, écoeurer, hospitaliser, pleurer, insuffiser, séparation, rabatteur, dae, craindre, dérive, terrible, vulgaire, anti-immigration, kalachnikov, arrestation, grognement, décapiter, tempête, consterner, burqa, fugue, archaïque, incarcérée, malmené, affrontement, massacre, fuite, décédé, casser, rude, bancal, fiasco, égoïste, tortueux, sanglant, détruite, diabétique, embûche, abandonner, subir, alerte, panique, brutal, rétracter, briser, balle, bêtise, inquiétante, adversaire, racaille, négligence, malfaiteur, enterrement, douteux, exaspérer, pétard, asphyxiant, kidnapper, arroger, merde, inaction, révolte, incohérence, enrage, hooligan, infériorisation, alarme, échouer, commissariat, claqu, illégau, désaveu, revendiquer, imposer, jungle, assistanat, chômage, ghetto, contredire, insalubre, poignardé, angoisse, suspendre, crise, pauvrete, fermer, inculper, déprimé, attaquant, dévaluer, forcé, dissoudre, rejet, controverser, expulsion, intempestif, inondation, militaire, disparaître, enfermer, arm, déplorable, ennemi, évacuer, frappé, abasourdi, gangrène, hostile, dangereuse, blessure, défausser, faux, déguerpier, exploser, attrist, fondamentalisme, problème, empoisonner, rejette, grave, extrémiste, rupture, caisse vide, accident, hostilité, triste, terrorisme, falsifier, peine, exploitation, résigner, écraser, milice, crevé, corruption, euroscepticisme, déni, terroriste, mécontentement, élitiste, séparer, éloigner, volte-face, arracher, miséreux, salafisme, désert, dévastée, kidnapping, afflux migratoire, krach, saturer, détester, persécuter, déséquilibré, complexité, terrifiante, faible, salafiste, déchéance, condamner, préoccupant, arrêter, dissimuler, afflux, sauvage, séquestration, incontrôlé, rébellion, convoquer, absence, désolé, trahie, porcherie, délinquance, "ex-braqueur", ignorance, lobotomiser, tabasser, rétorsion, épuiser, police, secte, timide, hain, crucifixion, scandale, diable, affronter, antisémite, malsain, malheureusement, désastreuse, fuité, enquêteur, naïf, désertification, attaquer, abusivement, envahisseur, problématique, orphelin, incendie, déformer, déconstruire, intense émotion, délinquant, coupure, hésitation, hurlante, révolution, défavorbal, oblige, "court-circuiter", refus, attaque, agressive, bassiner, jettent, tragique, intense, sorcier, inacceptable, contresens, commando,

régime autorisation, excès, brûlante, juger, soupçonner, émeute, nazi, modicité, combattre, manifesté, ingratitude, extrême, fardeau, aggravent, stigmatisation, analphabétisme, austérité, mal, exclure, absent, abîmer, mitrailleur, daesh, représaille, primaire, non déclarer, fragilité, extradé, protagoniste, errement, exil, expulser, traqu, confiance, surendettement, gêne, offensive, pauvre, ne pas donner bon image, racisme, jalouser, éclater, antidépresseur, chute, barbarie, défendre, effacer, surveillance, caprice, vieillissement, barrage, inquiéter, attentat - suicide, loupard, blesser, capricieux, clache, feu, xénophobe, embrouille, insoutenable, évacué, malaise, isolement, haine, inquiétude, trafic, corrompre, enquête, barber, vol, verrou, noyer, irrégulier, radicalisation, décapitation, obliger, durcissement, suicide, islamiste, mortel, débarqu, discriminer, manifester, inculpé, boue, brûler, impétie, effraye, conflit, épine, vandalisme, kamikaze, néonazisme, amère, démon, putsch, rançonner, opposition, fuir, sévère, pire, camp, façade, décourager, refermer, manifestation, conservateur, gâchis, ternir, victime, absurdité, procureur, quitter, frontière, "anti-système", peser, blocage, catapulte, dégradation, précaire, carcéral, anéanti, trahir, grille, raid, inconscience, suspect, doute, sidérer, agression, nier, rival, rompue, armée, fascisme, pléthorique, maléfique, bondir, carnage, honte, dissolution, grenade, inapte, désordre, passeur, émeute, saboter, démagogie, cri, agressiv, crime, fusillade, sacrifier, anti-migrant, policier